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Co-design workshops with consortium and stakeholders

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Summary

The Equal-Life project aims to investigate the combined effects of various exposures on children and adolescent mental health across different developmental stages. Important to this project is the collaboration with stakeholders.

This deliverable is a representation of all activities in five different meetings. Each meeting was structured according to different themes. The stakeholder fora in Ljubljana, Milano and in Helsinki were structured according to different interactive sessions. Different working methods were used. A range of potential outcomes were addressed.

The outcomes of the co-design workshops and stakeholder fora signify a important step toward developing a set of policy implementations, a toolbox and guidebook. These outcomes not only address the complexities of exposome data but also ensures its practical applicability in diverse settings. The collaborative and inclusive nature of this effort reflects a commitment to advancing our understanding of the exposome's impact on child mental health and cognitive development. The findings provide a foundation for informed policy decisions, promoting the integration of this toolbox into relevant research, healthcare, and educational initiatives.

Stakeholders are interested in practical implications of Equal-Life results. Stakeholders regard the Equal-Life toolbox as a set of tools that helps those interested in the Equal-Life project (at various levels) to explore, understand, and reuse the resulting outcomes. The Equal-Life guidebook should accompany the toolbox as a guide for practical use and help conceptualize what is being presented. It should assist the stakeholders to understand the connections between the multiple results displayed and what they mean for options of interventions.

It is in the interest of stakeholders that results show up options of interventions. In different countries (and regions, communities) power and finances are on different scales. Therefore, scientific data/results, and recommendations for interventions should be categorized by these scales.

Results and recommendations should be presented in a language that is understood by stakeholders. Due to the different languages, goals, motivations, and sense of urgency, the communication between scientists and stakeholders is a complex task. For the scientific community, nearness to decision-makers is important. Scientists should make use of communication experts were applicable in order to communicate their data results and recommendations.

1 Introduction

The task “Co-design workshops with consortium and stakeholders” related to D8.4 has the objective to establish a bi-directional dialogue between the Equal-Life project and (inter)national policy makers to 1) translate project results into effective children health policies and 2) inject knowledge about best practices and health policies into the project. This task ensures that the generated knowledge (on exposome, mechanisms, and health effects) is developed in line with the needs of the broader society, and that knowledge of the involved (public and private) stakeholders will help to interpret the results. This science-policy interaction gives a better understanding of the societal impact and relevance of the Equal-Life research both for the scientists within the project as for the stakeholders. We have identified key stakeholder (policy makers, regulators and research networks), and set up a formal co-design workshop and two stakeholder fora and established regular interaction between scientists and stakeholders.

In the 36 months reviews the requested action was to update the Gantt chart and the DoA. The focus of the deliverable has been adjusted with references to preliminary results. These were addressed in the last two stakeholder meetings. Additionally, the deliverable has been given examples of the co-design process and the description of expected outcomes. These were related to the context and the requirements of the toolbox and guidebook. These had strong links to the work of WP9. This D8.4 was previously submitted in April 2023, but now updated with information from two additional stakeholder meetings. Another update is expected in autumn 2024.

This deliverable is in a format of a demonstrator. It is a representation of all activities in five different meetings. Each meeting was structured according to different themes. The stakeholder fora in Ljubljana, Milano and in Helsinki were structured according to different interactive sessions.

- Stakeholder forum in Ljubljana, March 7 - 8, 2022
- Co-design workshop in Skopje, September 14 -15, 2022
- Stakeholder forum in Milan, November 16 -17, 2022
- Co-design workshop in Como, June 29-30, 2023
- Stakeholder forum in Helsinki September 7-8, 2023

Co-design workshop

Co-design is the act of creating interaction with stakeholders (policymakers, end-users) specifically within a design development process to ensure that the results meet their needs and are usable. Its aim is to create something not only for people, but also with them. Stakeholders can become creators of a product being actively involved in the creation process. Co-design is often a transdisciplinary process. The result can be a report (guidebook, guideline) or a product. In Equal-Life the co-design is a tool to enable stakeholders to use Equal-Life results for policy making or even to draft interventions. We conducted one co-design workshop in Skopje (see chapter 3).

Stakeholder forum

Stakeholder Forum means a platform open to representatives of institutions, national, regional and local authorities, organised interests and individual entities from different domains, higher education, research, associations, civil society and cluster organisations, as well as other interested parties from across a selected knowledge or policy focus.

The setup of the work process of co-design workshops or stakeholder forum is similar. The forum aims more at sending information between the participants. The co-design workshop aims at producing content related to the products that are seen as result of the project.

Here we describe the working process of the stakeholder fora and the co-design workshops. This working process is presented as a list. This is followed by a description of the outcomes of the collaborative effort between the Equal-Life partners and the stakeholders. This is also presented in a list.

Outline of the working process

The process of the co-design workshop and stakeholder forum uses a structured approach. This approach facilitates a codesign workshop/forum aimed at collaboratively developing 1) input for policy recommendations; 2) a tool or guidebook with support from diverse stakeholders. The process emphasizes open communication, active participation, and iterative feedback to ensure a well-rounded and inclusive final product. The following steps can be identified and have been used.

1. **Defining Objectives and Scope:** The workshop begins with a clear articulation of its purpose and goals. The focus is on defining the scope of the tool or guidebook, establishing boundaries to guide the collaborative process.
2. **Identifying Stakeholders:** Stakeholders, including end-users, subject matter experts, and decision-makers, are identified and invited to participate. The goal is to ensure a diverse representation that captures a broad range of perspectives.
3. **Pre-workshop Preparation:** Participants receive relevant information before the workshop, along with materials or resources to review. A communication platform is established to facilitate ongoing collaboration among stakeholders.
4. **Workshop Agenda:** A detailed agenda outlines the workshop activities, incorporating introductions, icebreakers, and specific design sessions. Time is allocated for brainstorming, prototyping, and feedback sessions.
5. **Facilitation Techniques:** Facilitation techniques are employed to encourage open communication, active participation, and equal contribution. The facilitator fosters a collaborative and inclusive environment where all voices are heard.
6. **Brainstorming:** Structured brainstorming sessions are conducted to generate ideas. Techniques such as mind mapping or affinity diagrams are employed, and participants are encouraged to share their perspectives and insights.
7. **Prototyping:** The design is broken down into smaller components, and participants work on creating prototypes or drafts of the tool or guidebook. Collaborative tools or physical materials are used to visualize ideas.
8. **Iterative Feedback:** Regular feedback sessions are facilitated, allowing stakeholders to review and provide input on prototypes and draft documents. Constructive criticism is encouraged, and concerns are addressed to refine the design.

9. Decision-Making: Facilitated decision-making sessions help prioritize features, content, or design elements. Techniques like dot voting or consensus building are used to reach agreements among stakeholders.

10. Documentation: Outcomes, decisions, and changes made during the workshop are thoroughly documented. A roadmap or action plan is created for the next steps in the development process.

11. Follow-up and Implementation: Stakeholders are kept informed about the workshop outcomes. Agreed-upon design changes are implemented, and stakeholders are continuously involved in the development process.

12. Communication: Ongoing communication is maintained with stakeholders throughout the development process. Regular updates and involvement in future iterations ensure sustained collaboration.

By following these steps, the codesign process became a dynamic and inclusive journey, harnessing the collective creativity and expertise of stakeholders to develop a valuable and well-received steps towards policy implications, a tool or guidebook.

Outline of the potential outcomes

We addressed in the different meetings the following outcomes. These demonstrate the significance and potential impact of this collaborative effort to improve the work of Equal-Life.

1. User-Defined Requirements for the policy development and the toolbox: Stakeholders, including researchers, healthcare professionals, non-governmental organisations, and policy makers, participate actively in defining specific requirements for policy implementations, the toolbox and guidebook.

2. Persona Profiles: Detailed persona profiles reflect the various stakeholders who will interact with the outcomes of Equal-Life. These personas provide a nuanced understanding of user perspectives, guiding the design process to be inclusive and user centric.

3. Exposome Mapping and Visualization Strategies: Stakeholders contribute to the development of effective exposome mapping and visualization strategies within the toolbox. This outcome ensures that the complex data related to exposome factors and their impact on child mental health can be communicated in a comprehensible and insightful manner.

4. Scope of impact assessment: Stakeholders contribute to identify which kinds of impact assessment are useful to incorporate into their daily practice. This also includes data sharing.

5. Use Case Scenarios: Collaboratively generated use case scenarios illustrate the practical applications of policies and the use of the toolbox in real-world situations. These scenarios not only refine the functionality of the toolbox but also demonstrate its potential value across diverse contexts. Case studies presented by stakeholders are part of this outcome.

6. Feature Prioritization: Stakeholders prioritize expectations of future policies and the toolbox features based on their perceived importance. This prioritization process ensures that the toolbox focuses on critical functionalities, aligning closely with the needs of users and maximizing its impact.

7. Prototypes and Demonstrator: Prototypes and demonstrator of the toolbox are developed, incorporating the identified features and design elements. Stakeholders provide valuable feedback on usability and effectiveness, facilitating an iterative improvement process.

8. Feedback and Iterative Improvement: An iterative feedback loop is established, allowing stakeholders to provide insights on the initial prototypes. This iterative approach ensures that the toolbox evolves in response to changing needs and expectations. This is also applied for the policy implementation process.

9. Documentation and Knowledge Sharing: Insights, decisions, and considerations from the workshop are documented, creating a knowledge base for future development. This documentation serves as a resource for transparency and informed decision-making, and for the content of the toolbox.

10. Work Plan for Implementation: A work plan is developed to outline the steps for implementing policies and incorporating the toolbox into healthcare practices, or educational settings. Roles and responsibilities are going to be defined to ensure ongoing collaboration.

11. Communication Strategy: A robust communication strategy will be established with WP10 to keep stakeholders informed of progress and updates related to the toolbox's and guidebook's development. This ongoing engagement ensures sustained interest and support.

12. Training and Support Needs: Potential training and support needs for users were identified, and plans for training sessions are under development. This task is the responsibility of WP9. This proactive approach ensures effective utilization of the toolbox within relevant sectors.

The following sections describe the different sessions that were organised with stakeholders.

Each of the meetings started with defining the objectives and scope of the meeting. Before the meeting we performed the steps of identifying the stakeholders (see D8.1), the pre-workshop preparation and the setting of the workshop agenda.

2 Stakeholder forum Ljubljana

This was the first encounter with stakeholders from outside the Equal-Life project. This section describes the activities of the stakeholder forum and the presentations. But first of all, we would like to describe the outcome of this workshop in relation with the first steps of the outline of the working process as describe on page 6.

About 25 people were present in the sessions, in addition to approximately 20 people online. Among the 25 live attendees were people from Slovenia, Croatia, Finland, Italy, and the Netherlands. Persons from Greece, Sweden, Slovakia, North Macedonia, and Germany were also present online. The group was about 50-50 divided between people who are focused in their work on public (mental) health and people who are focused on the physical environment. From the Equal-Life project, several researchers from different countries and institutes joined as well.

2.1 Theme 1: Scale on which results should focus

The first discussions were about on what scale (neighbourhood, city, country, etc.) the results of the Equal-Life research should focus, and whether a focus should possibly be placed on deprived neighbourhoods. The overall conclusion was that in each country the decision-making power and finances are on a different scale, and that data are often only relevant if they say something about that

scale. An example from Slovenia was that a benchmark had been developed in which regions are compared with each other. However, these regions are not decisive entities and do not manage their own finances, thus the results of this benchmark were ultimately not used for anything. It was suggested to determine scales that are translatable to each country (e.g. piece of street segment, urban block, neighbourhood, district, city, region, etc.) and to focus/classify results on these scales.

This session provided information on the steps 1 User-Defined Requirements for the policy development and the toolbox and 3. Exposome Mapping and Visualization Strategies of the outcome list. Additional notes on this session can be found in Annex 1.

2.2 Theme 2: Including the impact of environmental factors on mental health factors in all policy making

This conversation started with the question of whether Environmental Impact Assessments are necessary for effective policy making.

The environment was broadly defined to also include e.g. social media, climate change, fear of war, availability of space to play, etc. It was mentioned that the most relevant aspect here is the 'experience of the environment', instead of the objective design of the environment. Groups continued to discuss what it takes to include mental health and cognitive development as a factor in all policy fields. Impeding factors that were mentioned include difficulties of working together in an interdisciplinary way, uncertainty/unwillingness to look beyond your own policy field, not speaking the same language, and 'lack of mental health literacy'. It was also mentioned that too few evaluations are carried out on the effectiveness of initiatives, making it difficult to convince policy officers/politicians that their policy area has something to do with mental health. The complexity of the concept of mental health (and interventions related to it) was mentioned as a possible factor to connect policy fields: the topic is so complex and versatile that everyone's input is useful and necessary. Client and citizen participation/citizens' initiatives (speaking from the experience of the citizen in which all sectors come together naturally) were also mentioned as a connecting factor between fields.

This session provided information on the steps of the different forms of impact assessment. This refers to thinking about different domains of exposures to be addressed. Of course, this depends on the availability of the collected data in the cohorts.

2.3 Theme 3: Setting up effective youth participation

In the last round, we discussed how a bottom-up approach, with the participation of young people and children in research and policymaking can best be set up. The playful paradigm and the 15-minute city were mentioned as good examples. It was discussed that it is difficult to reach a representative group of young people.

This session addressed the topic of youth participation as part of the communication strategy. The stakeholders considered this an important topic. Link to outcome 11 of the list of outcomes.

Additional notes on this session can be found in Annex 1.

2.4 Mental health plans

We collected mental health plans (with a focus on children) to get a grip on some of the issues that stakeholders are facing in their work.

We discussed different mental health policy plans in different countries.

These plans have been used in the workshops and stakeholders for as examples of inspiration and of identification of problems in the domain of child mental health and cognitive development. This topic relates to item 9 Documentation and knowledge sharing of the outcome list. Additional notes on this session can be found in Annex 1.

3 Co-design workshop Skopje

A co-design workshop in Skopje, North Macedonia was held on the 14th and 15th of September 2022. This workshop discussed the progress and interaction with stakeholders in the Equal-Life project. But also, about the best ways of using the expected Equal-Life project results for implementing policies or interventions. What tools are available? How to best design policies? What are your needs as stakeholders working in the domain of children's mental health, cognitive development or protecting the social or physical environment? How can science and civil society organisations best cooperate?

The workshop was a live workshop. A total of 19 persons attended. The workshop took place at the Holiday Inn hotel in Skopje, North Macedonia.

The workshop was structured according to different themes. Each theme was introduced by one of the Equal-Life partners.

After a welcome and a general introduction, we discussed the different personas and stakeholder representation of the participants.

We used descriptions of personas of different kind of stakeholders in the workshop. The purpose of personas is to create reliable and realistic representations of a key audience. These representations should be based on qualitative and some quantitative user research. We wanted to get some insight of what kind of stakeholders are relevant for cooperation with researchers within the Equal-Life project. Not all possible stakeholders were present. The knowledge of which stakeholders were not present is also relevant information. We must consider how to reach out to those missing stakeholders. Some examples of the different personas that have been additionally developed by the participants are added in the annex 6.

In the introduction of the workshop the concept of persona profiles was used. This provides an understanding of user perspectives. During the workshop we could refer to these different personas to understand certain choices of the stakeholders.

3.1 Theme 1: Co-design tools

The session addressed questions on how to work towards implementation of results of Equal-Life into health and environmental policies considering children and youth. Which co-design tools are available? What can we learn from different examples? Which tools could benefit your work?

The working method was a world café setup with 4 groups and 4 questions (4 x 15 minutes). This roundtable discussed the following questions:

- Do you have experience and lessons learned regarding co-design or other participatory approaches? Do you use co-design in your work? Do you use co-design in your work, in your organisation?
- Do you collaborate with other professionals, with scientists, with citizens?
- Do you need to shift policies, projects and/or budgets to children's mental health and cognitive development?
- Do you have tips regarding implementing new tools, new (scientific) evidence in your organisation, your work?

The main considerations were grouped according to the topics: 1) co-design process; 2) awareness raising; 3) co-design tools; and 4) cooperation. The participants gave a broad range of suggestions.

Co-designing process: Learning from and listening to stakeholders needs investment (time), from the start, without presumptions. Non-linear process, sometimes you need to go back to previous steps. Listen to people that are not enthusiastic. Have people in the centre of this process, for example as 'idea generators'. Consider rewarding stakeholders. Stress the advantages of co-design, without mentioning the concept of co-designing explicitly. And outputs / results of such processes are not set at the beginning of the (co-design) process.

Awareness raising: we need good stories and good 'storytellers' to bring the topic to the public and to politicians. Positive stories, tailored to regions and countries (culture specific). Shift to prevention approach (policies and funding). More long-term and structural projects (programmes) are needed. There is still a stigma in various countries. Citizens (voters) can plead for a shift to prevention with the politicians.

Tools: important to know the target group, tailor-made products. Best practices. Issues are money and staffing. Various examples such as Lifelines, on data collection. Visual and interactive. Specify the (governmental) level that is addressed. Communication, films, storytelling, etc. Tools for presenting data. Do not reinvent the wheel.

Cooperation: A distinction needs to be made between politicians and administration within governments. Consider who is in charge, which influences the results of the collaboration. The ones in charge define the agenda, the expected outcomes et cetera. Different channels for collaboration, see participation ladder. However, even the one-way communication (lowest step) is difficult. People using TikTok do not want to read scientific information. Twitter, with scientific information, is not used by 'the people'. Thus consider the social media source for communication. Collect information from different experts / perspectives and combine that in the communication. Make success visible, which

might be different for different stakeholders. And identify 'what are successes for these different stakeholder groups from the beginning.

This session addressed mainly the prototyping of user-defined requirements of the outcomes. Communication, knowing your target groups and collaborating were highlighted as important outcomes.

3.2 Theme 2: Working on application of tools based on Equal- life results

This session the participants discussed questions such as: What tools suit the different stakeholders? How flexible should we be in applying different tools? How about visualization?

- Feedback was given on data and on structure of the toolbox / demonstrator. The latter has to be further developed. In spreading / disseminating the tool we need to consider language. Next step is to select the 'data themes' and then detail the (level and type of) data (needs).
- Data visualisation: tip was given to look at the example of the Dutch "Kansenkaart.nl" (see <https://kansenkaart.nl/klasouderslaaginkomen#6.47/52.29/5.285>)
- Data in the toolbox will be both from Equal-Life and from other existing sources. The different WPs will deliver algorithms and functions, and probably not data. We do not expect anonymised data. But aggregation of data would be feasible.
- See presentation in annex 2.

This session addressed the usability and effectiveness of the tools that Equal-Life is producing. Feedback on data and data visualization were strong arguments by the stakeholders to be addressed. These points are linked to Exposome mapping, the need for visualization strategies and development of prototypes.

3.3 Theme 3: Working towards translation of scientific results

During this session, the participants discussed questions such as: How easy to understand need the results be? Do we have disconnections between scientists and policymakers? What are barriers? We used a presentation and group discussion. The presentation was focused on tipping points of social behaviour and adoption of change in behaviour by people. See presentation in annex 3.

Summary of feedback given.

- Scientist's opinions are needed, in a way, to translate into policy. The message needs to be clear and with a simple conclusion. Scientists have no contact with policy makers (in various countries). Whereas scientists working in e.g., national public health institutes have more regular contact with policy makers and citizens and are better fit for this. Due to their position, as advisors to ministers; these professionals could be the 'storytellers'. 'Nearness' is an important factor.
- Motivation and interests of scientists can differ from the needs of policy makers. Selection is needed of what kind of analyses you make on your data. The main focus in writing is that other

scientists can replicate research and not particular that others can implement the results in practice.

- Lessons from the corona pandemic on scientists communicating to the public and policy makers / politicians involving scientists should be learnt. Suggestion: Prepare 1/2 pages for politicians/policy makers.

This session addressed the topic of item 10 of the outcome list. Many suggestions were given on how to translate scientific results into the policy domain. Additional notes on this session can be found in Annex 2.

3.4 Theme 4: Interventions ‘bridging the gap’ as a tool to improve health for all

In this session, we asked participants to draw on their experience with interventions to map out the steps and factors that they think are part of a generic intervention process. As part of this, we asked to describe examples of social inequalities from their work and consider how the intervention process can be designed to better address such inequalities. We then focused on interventions relating to the built environment – such as what stakeholders know from their neighbourhood or city – to think about important aspects of the intervention process when thinking about how to account for social inequalities in environmental exposures.

This workshop session comprised of various discussions and then a collaborative piece of group work. The initial question that the group discussed together asked participants what an ‘intervention’ was to them, as in what this term means. Then, the group was asked to form a continuum with each person choosing a specific intervention. One end of this continuum represented interventions that exclusively address a physical exposure(s) (including the built environment), while the other end of the spectrum represented an intervention that was exclusively about addressing a social exposure(s). The idea behind this was to prompt discussion about how interventions focusing on the built environment, such as the way a city is built, also has implications in terms of social issues and that it is therefore important to consider issues relating to social inequalities, for example, even if the intervention is not primarily a ‘social’ intervention.

We used an iterative process in that participants were encouraged to start the exercise thinking about the intervention process in general terms, before then being asked to extend this thinking to relate to issues of equity and social inequalities specifically. For example, after brainstorming a general flowchart of intervention steps in groups, each group was then asked to think about social inequalities generally and where it would be important to consider such issues during an intervention process. Finally, participants were asked to consider specific pre-prepared questions relating to equity considerations and whether/how they thought they could be used as part of the intervention process. Physical and social domain must be involved. It is important that we learn from the different perspectives and language used, for example, by the different stakeholders in relation to the intervention process, as their experience varies significantly. In the presentation of the case studies these different policy domains must be identified, clarified as well.

The details of this session are described in Annex 2 under Theme Interventions ‘bridging the gap’ as a tool to improve health for all

This session addressed item 5 the use of case scenarios. The focus of this session was on the social exposome. This was regarded as very important by the stakeholders. Additional notes on this session can be found in Annex 2.

3.5 Theme 5: Spectrum of prevention

This was an open session to brainstorm on what kind of prevention should be on the policy agenda. Also, the question was posed on what the expected trends are in children's mental health and cognitive development. And: Why can research be beneficial to change policy? What studies and tools should be used?

The participants provided suggestions on how to develop prevention strategies. See details of their answers in Annex 2.

This session relates to the item of making a workplan for implementation (item 10) and featuring prioritization (item 6). The suggestions show a broad range of topics. These should be considered n further steps in the Equal-Life work. Additional notes on this session can be found in Annex 2.

3.6 Theme 6: What are the next steps?

The participants, both stakeholder and consortium members, were positive about the workshop. They thought it would be very useful to continue this kind of work. Suggestions were given on strengthening the network of stakeholders. Communication to all stakeholders. Share communication strategy. How is the communication flow to professionals? WHO, EU, ministries of health, regions etc. Have stakeholders talking about their work. Create and share more concrete examples from WPs. Rebuilding the demonstrator. More and better connections to other WPs. There is a need to know what is going on. Participants need a few preliminary results or outputs for involving stakeholders. Involve youth in all WPs, as stakeholders, we are talking about their lives. As well as parents. Stakeholder community building, inform about who is coming to the next meeting. Use LinkedIn. Regular updates on the (whole) project, like a newsletter.

This session showed the importance of developing a communication strategy (item 11).

4 Stakeholder forum Milano

Introduction

The Milan stakeholder forum aimed to bring together professionals in the domains of mental health and environmental health to discuss 1) exposure to the physical and social environment of children; 2) the use of tools as a strategy to bridge the science and policy domain; and 3) using the future Equal-Life project results for implementing policies or interventions to improve children's environments and

mental health. 17 stakeholders were (part-time) present, together with 23 researchers (5 of them online) from the Equal-Life project.

The forum took place November 16-17, 2022, at the Starhotel Ritz in Milan, Italy. The first day was dedicated to presentations on work from Equal-Life researchers and stakeholders, followed by world café discussions. The first day was closed with a workshop on the logic model that is developed within Equal-Life as a tool to encourage thinking about social inequalities in urban planning interventions.

The second day opened with a workshop on how to evaluate children's access to public outdoor play space, research that is also performed within Equal-Life. The rest of the day was dedicated to discussing policy recommendations and useful interventions in the environmental mental health domain.

The hands-on workshops provided the Equal-Life project researchers with valuable input to improve the presented tools. Some conclusions:

- Stakeholders want to have a role in Equal-Life, for example in piloting Equal-Life (draft) outcomes (knowledge and tools) and in co-designing of or commenting on Equal-Life deliverables.
- Interaction with Equal-Life researchers and involvement of stakeholders in (specific) work (packages) need to be facilitated and increased, for example in (in-person) meetings as well as in one-to-one settings and online working groups.

This stakeholder forum addressed the following items of the list of outcomes.

- User-Defined Requirements for the policy development and the toolbox
- Exposome Mapping and Visualization Strategies
- Feature Prioritization
- Scope of impact assessment
- Prototypes and Demonstrator
- Feedback and Iterative Improvement and expectations. This is also applied for the policy implementation process.
- Documentation and Knowledge Sharing
- Work Plan for Implementation
- Communication Strategy

Content of the meeting

Three presentations were provided by Equal-Life researchers to provide an overview of the project.

See for more information the Deliverable 8.2.

4.1 Equal-Life guidebook and toolbox

The guidebook and toolbox session were a parallel activity that ran throughout the forum. It was introduced by a short presentation that explained the intent and current definition of what we call the toolbox and guidebook. The definitions are under continuous discussion. Since the first stakeholder meeting in March 2022 (Ljubljana, Slovenia) the responsible partners have been requesting feedback from internal (Equal-Life) and external (stakeholders) partners, which is part of an iterative process. The current understanding of the toolbox and guidebook are as follows:

- The toolbox should be a tool, or set of tools, which helps those interested in the Equal-Life project (at various levels) to explore, understand, and reuse the resulting outcomes.
- The guidebook should accompany the toolbox as a guide to practical use and help conceptualize what is being presented. It should assist the user to understand the connections between the multiple results displayed.

The input received was similar to the collected ideas in the previous stakeholder meetings as it focuses on the development of tools that can allow guiding and facilitated access to the project contents such as deliverables, research questions, and features considered in the analysis. Strong interest was also expressed in explanations and training on analysis methods and software developed during the project, with consequent interest in dedicated training sessions.

The stakeholders' input was helpful for the outcomes of Prototyping the toolbox.

4.2 World café discussions on Equal-Life presentations

The section describes the input given by some PIs of the Equal-Life project, and also by some stakeholders. The interaction with the stakeholders provided information on the Feedback and Iterative Improvement and expectations, Feature Prioritization and on Documentation and knowledge sharing.

We used the World café method. In annex 3 are short descriptions of the different sessions.

4.3 Using a logic model as a tool to encourage thinking about social inequalities in urban planning interventions

For this workshop session ran by Jenny Ahrens (UB), the goal was to evaluate the applicability of the Logic Model for Equity Assessment using an exemplary intervention on bicycle infrastructure based on the workshop participants' expertise. To do this, five groups were formed, and each group focussed on the three main parts of an intervention: Planning – Implementation – Evaluation.

During the discussion, the following three questions were our guiding questions:

- What tools similar to the logic model are you currently using at work (e.g., guiding questions, frameworks, other models)?
- Can you see the logic model being used in your work?
- What could be added or changed in order to make the logic model a more useful tool?

As for the different three phases, it was noted that an impact assessment would be valuable within the planning phase and that evaluation needs to be implemented within all phases.

The main takeaway from the discussion with stakeholders and members of Equal-Life was that it needs to be made very clear that this Logic Model for Equity Assessment is not another process-model but is about assessing the equity aspects in the three main phases of an intervention. Ideas to improve this was to emphasize this even in the visual model by using “trigger words”.

This session related to the Scope of impact assessment. Based on the feedback the logic model could be improved.

4.4 Evaluating children's access to public outdoor play space

In the session on Evaluating Children's Access to Public Outdoor Play Space, Roos Teeuwen and Achilleas Psyllidis (TU Delft) collected knowledge from the Equal-Life stakeholders in an interactive workshop session. TU Delft aims to measure children's access to play spaces in cities, to be used for the enrichment of the Equal-Life cohort and school study data sets. The goal of this session was threefold: to collaboratively identify the factors that limit or promote children's access to play space; to connect these factors to elements in the urban environment; and to assess the latest work-in-progress approach of TU Delft in measuring children's access to play space.

First, RT (TUD) introduced the topic to the stakeholders and provided them with a short overview of the theory that the workshop was built upon. Then, stakeholders were asked to contribute with suggestions of factors that limit or that promote children's access to play space as keywords, followed by a brief plenary discussion of the most prevalent limiting (i.e., lack of safety or security, traffic, and lack of places suiting age or multiple generations of users) and promoting factors (i.e., safety, other children, informal places to play, and equipment for children with reduced abilities).

Second, both stakeholders and Equal-Life participants split into 6 groups, each at their own table, to discuss children's accessibility in a specific urban case: 3 tables focused on Ljubljana, Slovenia, and 3 tables on Milan, Italy. Participants familiar with either Milan or Ljubljana were presented with the corresponding city, while others were spread over tables to ensure variety in expertise and geographical background. At each table, an Equal-Life moderator guided the process. Participants discussed photos and maps of the city at hand and pinpointed what could limit or promote children to access play spaces.

Third, participants were presented with a map overlay on top of the map of the second round, made by TU Delft to model children's access to play space. Specifically, these overlays showed places they identified that may attract children's play (i.e., playgrounds and small parks), or that may be a barrier to children who want to access a space to play in the city (i.e., transport and natural infrastructures). Participants discussed to what extent they agreed with the barriers and places presented on the maps, as well as what should be omitted or added to better reflect practice.

Throughout the second and third rounds, participants contributed their knowledge by means of annotations, drawings, and sticky notes. Participants also elaborated on experiences from their own life or town, which were captured in audio recordings. TU Delft will use these to understand the potential and limitations of using such data to model children's access to play space in the Equal-Life project.

Preliminary take-away messages from the participants to TUD include: The size and shape of parks, time of day, movement trajectories, and surrounding land use and activities matter when assessing children's access to play space; Good quality infrastructure is important; And knowledge from local experts or children is crucial to get a complete understanding of children's access to public outdoor play space in the urban environment at hand.

This output of this session will enable TUD to improve the Exposome Mapping and Visualization Strategies.

4.5 Policy recommendation perspectives

INCHES (PvdHI) introduced the session with a short presentation on the ecological doughnut model and the DPSIR model. The doughnut model by Kate Raworth (2012) is a visual framework for sustainable development, combining the concept of planetary boundaries with the complementary concept of social boundaries. The DPSIR model (drivers, pressures, state, impact, and response model of intervention) is a causal framework for describing the interactions between society and the environment.

These models were developed in the context of planetary health and the environmental sciences, to describe and clarify complex systems. The participants were invited to think of applying an adapted version of the DPSIR model to the context of children's mental health and cognitive development. The results from the discussions on drivers, pressures, status, mediators, and outcomes are on the next page.

This session had the aimed to give the stakeholders input for future steps in implementation of policies and interventions. This relates to documentation and knowledge sharing.

4.7 What are the next steps?

In this final session, the stakeholders and Equal-Life researchers split into two separate groups. The stakeholders reflected on the tips and tops of the stakeholder forum from their perspective. The Equal-Life researchers discussed next steps to take in the stakeholder activities.

5 Co-design workshop Como

A co-design workshop in Como, Italy was held on the 29th and 30th of June 2023. This workshop discussed the progress and interaction with stakeholders in the Equal-Life project. The best ways of using the expected Equal-Life project results for implementing policies or interventions were discussed. How should we design the tools? How to incorporate the generated data from Equal-Life in the design of policies? What are you the needs as stakeholders working in the domain of children's mental health, cognitive development to link Equal-Life results to the work that stakeholders do? How can science and civil society organisations best cooperate?

The workshop was a live workshop. A total of 15 persons attended (live 12, 3 online. The workshop took place at the Politenico in Como.

Sessions were conducted on how to read frameworks and different conceptual models on exposures, mediators, settings and life course stages. Another session discussed the use of tools and how these

should be designed. Another session dealt with the reflection on the prioritization of research questions of Equal-Life and their link to daily practice of the stakeholders. A session on social exposome looked at the integration of social and physical domain. This was considered as very important by the stakeholders. Two final sessions were conducted on 1) Data and harmonization; and 2) Conceptual modelling with semantic technologies.

Introduction presentation on conceptual models

Presentation WP1 (DS - Partner ZEUS): formulate theories and mechanisms -> framework and different conceptual models (exposures, mediators, settings, life course stages).

Some mentioned highlights:

Social practices affect the impact, as well as social and physical environments. Translated into research questions, which are “tested’ in in-depth studies (sleep study and preschool study) and in cohort studies, including enrichment of the data. Results will be available end of 2023 / beginning of 2024 (externally).

An identification of **key exposures** within the human exposome; this could for example be exposures like access to play areas, noise levels during sleep, and quality of interaction between child and parent, depending upon the health outcomes.

Discussion on the concept of **mediator**, such as sleep and stress. How do stakeholders use that?

Suggested by stakeholder: It is an ‘outcome’ that is an entrance point for unpicking/understanding what’s behind this. An inventory on stress among parents now includes a question on whether one *minds* experiencing stress. Poverty is an essential factor, the main factor, as well. Poverty is part of the social exposome. Housing in combination with poverty.

Poverty is not used as a term in Equal-Life but can be found in the ‘inequalities’ perspective of the research.

Adding another mediator, such as access to (social / health) services could be considered?

This session provided insights on User-Defined Requirements for the policy development and the toolbox, the Exposome Mapping and Visualization Strategies, the Scope of impact assessment (including data sharing), the Prototypes and Demonstrator (related to the toolbox), Feedback and Iterative Improvement and expectations. This is also applied for the science-policy implementation process. Feature Prioritization and Documentation and Knowledge Sharing.

- Work Plan for Implementation
- Communication Strategy

Session on tools

Make a distinction between types of stakeholders. Who are you addressing? Information for decision making. (Inter)national level, city level, community level and settings level. Make the tool according to *simplicity* principles.

See for details on the stakeholder reflections annex 4.

This session provided information to develop the prototype and demonstrator towards a toolbox.

Session on research questions moderated by INCHES

Tables with the research questions considered in the project were presented in the discussion. The questions had been sent in advance to stakeholders in order to have time to read and understand them.

See for details on the stakeholder reflections annex 4.

See annex 9 for tables with research questions. Initial use for names of stakeholders.

Session on Translation of scientific results into tools moderated by Quantia

The insights from the co-creation workshop in Como provided a valuable understanding of how stakeholders utilize tools in their professional environments and offered feedback on the demonstrator's advantages and disadvantages.

Main interest was seen in all outputs from WP4 and low interest in WP5 for stakeholders, except for the maps (and higher for researchers).

Related to the development of a toolbox several suggestions were provided. Stakeholders mentioned preferred formats: guidelines, visuals, 'easy' website, policy brief, communication material, interactive webpages.

Action: raise importance of discussing preliminary results with stakeholders during upcoming catch-up session. Researchers need to learn to communicate with / to non-academics. Make the language work for the end-user.

This session provided input for the workplan on implementation and information to develop the prototype and demonstrator towards a toolbox.

Session on social exposome moderated by UB, INCHES and NIJZ

Session started with an explanation about the social exposome.

Social exposome: a novel conceptual framework. Goal a realistic portrayal of the complex social environment. Characteristics of the framework: Multidimensionality, reciprocity and timing and continuity. See paper at:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0013935123012896?via%3Dihub>

Three pathways are identified in the model developed by UB: empowerment, resilience and susceptibility or vulnerability, and embodiment as additional feature.

Integration of social and physical exposomes. Question by stakeholder: Why integration? Answer: To understand mechanisms / pathways that drive the patterning / combinations of exposures and how they together and holistically affect health.

Starting point is to develop reliable and valid metrics to measure the complex external environment, comprised from social and physical indicators.

Integration of social and physical domains leads to another starting point towards a holistic external exposome concept.

See Annex 4 on discussion notes, on interaction session and on data harmonization session.

This session related to knowledge sharing and feature prioritization. Input is valuable for adapting the social exposome model.

Interactive session on Prioritising data (categories)

We wanted to know which categories of data are important in the view of stakeholders. Different categories of data were mentioned. Prioritised categories are mental health, fluid intelligence, socio-demographic factors, psychosocial stress, relationships and social support, educational mobility, health characteristics, learning and teaching conditions, living conditions.

Although all have (some) importance.

Reflections on this 'exercise':

- We should have done this at the start of the research project.
- Combining research and practitioner's arguments – interdisciplinary approach
- Combine these priorities with the research questions priorities.

This session provided input for the feature prioritization of outcomes of the project in order to match stakeholder's expectations with the potential output of the toolbox.

Session on Conceptual modelling with semantic technologies (MB, Quantia)

Within Equal-Life a semantic knowledge search tool will be developed: a tool to help you finding a specific document. What is an ontology? A model of (some aspect of) the world. Introduces vocabulary relevant to the domain. Specifies meaning (semantics) of terms. Formalised using suitable logic. Shared among multiple organisations.

Creating classes. Creating subclasses. Creating a class instance. For example: artist is a class. Painter and sculptor are subclasses of the artist class. And Leonardo is a painter (hence, also an artist). Leonardo is not a class. And then creating additional class instances: for example, Da Vinci, age, birth date. Creating class instances through class properties, for example: Leonardo paints the Monalisa (painting), Michelangelo paints the Sistine Chapel (painting), Michelangelo sculpts the David (sculpture) . And then an AI tool can know that Leonardo creates the Monalisa or that Michelangelo creates the Sistine Chapel and the David.

Stakeholder help needed to improve /reflect on the tool.

Feedback stakeholders: search the evidence and best practice, take theory and implement that. Not interested in what is at the back of that (website, tool etc). Technique versus content.

Search engine optimisation. Conceptual model of Equal-Life is the ontology for the tool prototype. To be validated by stakeholders (e.g. in stakeholder forum in Helsinki). Have a practitioner and IT expert working side by side.

Organising the input for the machine learning is an important step. Irene: note, there are more conceptual models in Equal-Life, thus need to use the definition documents / go a layer deeper. Suggestion: prepare an example to further discuss / pre-test with stakeholders. Starting point for the ontology could be the conceptual model of WP1.

Final conclusion:

A Demonstrator version of the toolbox/guidebook was prepared and reviewed with stakeholders at the WP8 co-creation meeting in Como. Additionally, an Editorial Board was formed to organize and incorporate results and findings from the Equal-Life project into the toolbox and guidebook. This board, adopting a top-down approach, comprises members with diverse expertise in areas such as tools and training, knowledge management, guidebook and toolbox development, stakeholder expertise, and communication and coordination. Their goal is to make the project's outcomes easily understandable and relevant to the public.

Session was related to prototyping of the toolbox.

6 Stakeholder forum Helsinki

A stakeholder forum was conducted at 7 and 8 September 2023 in City Hall, Helsinki. This meeting was organized by the stakeholder from the City of Helsinki. There were 14 stakeholders present and 14 representatives of the Equal-Life project.

The aim of the meeting was to give input towards the way of the development of policy recommendations, towards the content of the toolbox and good practices/requirements for training to implement policy recommendations and tools.

Thursday 7th September

The meeting started with a short explanation of Equal-Life research, the conceptual framework and the program of the 2-day workshops organized by WP8 (stakeholder involvement) and WP9 (toolbox and training).

An introduction was given on the conceptual framework, the totality of internal, social and physical exposures, over a lifetime, on better understanding the causes of and processes related to mental health and cognitive functioning, with potential mediating pathways, and about providing a possibility for interventions along the life course.

Expected results: early life exposure to urban planning related factors (noise, air), social factors (parental stress, social economic), biomarkers related to environmental and social exposures.

Presentations were given on:

- Overview preliminary results
- Measuring access to public spaces
- Presentation on enriching the environmental exposome: road traffic flow prediction and noise modelling
- Social exposome
- Conceptual framework

See for details on these presentations Annex 4. These presentation updated the stakeholders on the state of the art of the work done in Equal-Life. Feedback was given by the stakeholders.

Friday 8th September

Presentations were given by stakeholders on their work related to topics that are addressed in the Equal-Life project.

The sessions are related to knowledge sharing. It gives the Equal-Life consortium insight in which kind of policy implementations and potential interventions are important.

Toolbox and guidebook (AS, Quantia)

The stakeholder forum in Helsinki produced beneficial feedback for the revised prototype of the toolbox/guidebook. Involvement of stakeholders in broader communication of Equal-Life results is crucial – and offered!

Discussed items for the Toolbox modules are stakeholders, visualization, semantic knowledge exploration, connection and sharing modules. In more detail the Stakeholder module should be an explorative website with clickable elements. Feedback has been tested in previous stakeholder workshops. The updated website is presented in this workshop for comments.

Tools are broadly defined, and a broad selection will be presented, but not hosted on the website but through linkages to the 'owners' of the specific tools. The website will be open for everyone and will have an explorative part.

Use storytelling (workshops) for the researchers in order to collect stories, content for the website.

Suggestions:

- Instead of a website or in addition to the website consider developing an app.
- Link to other websites and dashboards such as UNICEF.

This session provided input on the prototyping of the toolbox. This is also related to visualization, knowledge sharing, communication and training and other support needs.

7 Conclusion / Next steps

This chapter highlights the outcomes of the co-design workshops and stakeholder fora that brought together diverse stakeholders to collaboratively shape the development steps towards using the project results for potential policy implementations. And moreover, for the development of a toolbox and guidebook. The toolbox aims to advance our understanding of the exposome's role in children's mental health change during childhood and adolescence, and children's cognitive development. The following outcomes demonstrate the significance and potential impact of this collaborative effort.

1. User-Defined Requirements for the policy development and the toolbox: Stakeholders, including researchers, healthcare professionals, non-governmental organisations, and policy makers, actively participated in defining specific requirements for policy implementations, the toolbox and guidebook. This inclusive approach ensures that these goals address the unique needs and expectations of diverse user groups. The contribution by the stakeholders increased the knowledge

about what is needed to link the project results to policy implications. Their practical considerations of policy making was very useful.

2. Persona Profiles: Detailed persona profiles were created, reflecting the various stakeholders who will interact with the outcomes of Equal-Life. These personas provide a nuanced understanding of user perspectives, guiding the design process to be inclusive and user centric. This is helpful in the interdisciplinary communication and dissemination of the results at the end of the project.

3. Exposome Mapping and Visualization Strategies: Stakeholders contributed to the development of effective exposome mapping and visualization strategies within the toolbox. This outcome ensures that the complex data related to exposome factors and their impact on child mental health can be communicated in a comprehensible and insightful manner. The examples that were used in the different meetings were improved along the way. The main request from stakeholders was that we start with a very simple presentation of topics/tools and each user of tools can go deeper and reach more complex level of the tools we are developing

4. Scope of impact assessment: Stakeholders contribute to identify which kinds of impact assessment are useful to incorporate into their daily practice. Data sharing and the availability of data were issues that were raised by the stakeholders. This needs to be incorporated in the final stages of the project.

5. Use Case Scenarios: Collaboratively generated use case scenarios illustrate the practical applications of policies and the use of the toolbox in real-world situations. These scenarios not only refine the functionality of the toolbox but also demonstrate its potential value across diverse contexts. Several case studies presented by stakeholders are part of this outcome. See the presentations by the stakeholders in chapter 6, pages 41-43.

6. Feature Prioritization: Stakeholders prioritized expectations of future policies and the toolbox features based on their perceived importance. This prioritization process ensures that the toolbox focuses on critical functionalities, aligning closely with the needs of users and maximizing its impact. An example given by the stakeholders is make a clear link between the exposures in the physical and social domain.

7. Prototypes and Demonstrator: Prototypes and demonstrator of the toolbox were created, incorporating the identified features and design elements. Stakeholders provided valuable feedback on usability and effectiveness, facilitating an iterative improvement process. For example that a web based tool should try to be a one-click button approach site.

8. Feedback and Iterative Improvement: An iterative feedback loop was established, allowing stakeholders to provide insights on the initial prototypes. This iterative approach ensures that the toolbox evolves in response to changing needs and expectations. This is also applied for the policy implementation process. The stakeholders were strong in giving feedback based on their expertise in gained at their work.

9. Documentation and Knowledge Sharing: Insights, decisions, and considerations from the workshop were documented, creating a knowledge base for future development. This documentation serves as a resource for transparency and informed decision-making and for the content of the toolbox.

10. Work Plan for Implementation: A work plan for 2023 and 2024 was developed to outline the steps for implementing policies and incorporating the toolbox into healthcare practices, or

educational settings. Roles and responsibilities are going to be defined to ensure ongoing collaboration.

11. Communication Strategy: A robust communication strategy will be established with WP10 to keep stakeholders informed of progress and updates related to the toolbox's and guidebook's development. This ongoing engagement ensures sustained interest and support. Suggestions were made by the stakeholders to support this process.

12. Training and Support Needs: Potential training and support needs for users were identified, and plans for training sessions are under development. This proactive approach ensures effective utilization of the toolbox within relevant sectors.

Conclusion: The outcomes of these co-design workshops and stakeholder fora signify a significant step toward developing a set of policy implementations and a toolbox and guidebook that not only addresses the complexities of exposome data but also ensures its practical applicability in diverse settings. The collaborative and inclusive nature of this effort reflects a commitment to advancing our understanding of the exposome's impact on child mental health. The findings presented here provide a foundation for informed policy decisions, promoting the integration of this toolbox into relevant research, healthcare, and educational initiatives.

Stakeholders are interested in practical implications of Equal-Life results. Stakeholders regard the Equal-Life toolbox as a set of tools that helps those interested in the Equal-Life project (at various levels) to explore, understand, and reuse the resulting outcomes. The Equal-Life guidebook should accompany the toolbox as a guide for practical use and help conceptualize what is being presented. It should assist the stakeholders to understand the connections between the multiple results displayed and what they mean for options of interventions.

It is in the interest of stakeholders that results show up options of interventions. In different countries (and regions, communities) power and finances are on different scales. Therefore, scientific data/results, and recommendations for interventions should be categorized by these scales.

Results and recommendations should be presented in a language that is understood by stakeholders. Due to the different languages, goals, motivations, and sense of urgency, the communication between scientists and stakeholders is a complex task. For the scientific community, nearness to decision-makers is important. Scientists should make use of communication experts where applicable in order to communicate their data results and recommendations.

Not only is the communication between scientists and stakeholders an issue. There are different groups of stakeholders with different backgrounds. Interdisciplinarity and collaboration between stakeholder groups are essential in regard to effective interventions. The youngsters themselves and their parents should not be forgotten as important stakeholder groups. The research and derived interventions are about their lives.

Stakeholder involvement is not a one-direction communication from the scientific community to stakeholders. Co-design means learning from and listening to stakeholders. This is essential from the start. Stakeholders' needs can guide scientific work (what factors to be considered, what exposures, outcomes, etc.). Stakeholders can help scientists to interpret the results of data analysis in terms of feasible options for improvement. Besides going from scientific data analysis and results to interventions, the scientific process can start from interventions that are evaluated including the scientific explanation of mechanisms underlying success or failure of interventions. This, again, would add to scientific conceptual modelling building.

For the following project period the next steps are:

- New events on stakeholder involvement in the Equal-Life events are planned.
- Work on the toolbox and the guidebook continues.
- The ongoing analyses of cohort, school and in-depth study data will provide lots of results and several conceptual models on exposome – mechanism – outcome relationships.
- Once, the results of the data analyses of the different Equal-Life teams are available, a joined workshop with stakeholders and scientists from other WPs will be planned. Within the workshop, stakeholders and Equal-Life scientists together will interpret the results, identify common features of the different models and discuss evidence-based recommendations for (categories of) interventions aiming to improve children's mental health and cognitive development.
- Even if it turns out that Equal-Life results are preliminary and that it is too early to formulate scientific evidence-based recommendations for interventions, this is an important outcome for the discussion with stakeholders. Then, both, stakeholders and scientists together can identify gaps and recommend next steps for future scientific work that provide useful information for effective interventions. Such future research may consist of the scientific evaluation of interventions on children's health and development – making the continuing collaboration of stakeholders and scientists essential. Important feedback during the discussions in the stakeholders' workshops and fora so far in Equal-Life is that such scientific accompaniment of interventions would be considered by stakeholders as very helpful and useful.

8 Partners / Equal-Life contact information

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9 Annexes

Annex 1 Additional notes on workshop in Ljubljana

Theme 1

Some additional observations from participants:

- Multi-level model; interventions on all levels should feed into each other
- Evaluations of effectiveness are missing; what do interventions achieve?
- Social dimension and cognitive dimension are very important; very different for mental health (vs. physical)
- It is easier for people to reflect on physical rather than mental health
- Exposome research is complex & multidimensional; interventions on different levels are necessary
- Example of intervention: <https://young.scot/>

Practical aspects: need of stakeholders that research delivers practical outputs; are the researchers aware of stakeholder needs? How to involve stakeholders in the next (research) steps? Matching Equal-Life work with stakeholders (needs). Even if they are aware of their needs, they may not be able to help. For example, data needed are not available at the level that would allow analysis. For example, data on health/wellbeing are only available for municipalities in Slovenia. Those do not allow studies at neighbourhood level for example. Maybe Environmental Atlas can be promoted as source of at least some information on the environment. This is available at least for some examples for the local level. For example noise maps are available at neighbourhood level but only for areas defined in Directive 2002/49/EC. http://gis.arso.gov.si/atlasokolja/profile.aspx?id=Atlas_Okolja_AXL@Arso

Theme 3

Finland works with a youth portal, in which young people are asked questions about policy plans. A link to these questions is shared in various ways via social media, with extra effort being put into engaging groups of young people who are out of the picture – for example via Discord discussion platforms and TikTok. The importance of training children and young people in policy participation (for example at school), giving them the confidence that their input counts, and improving the involvement of less privileged children /young people was also discussed. As a good example, it was mentioned how children in Canada are encouraged from primary school to speak publicly and to be politically engaged.

Finally, a participant from Scotland talked about how legislating the children's right to involvement in policymaking opened doors to developing approaches to be effective in youth participation.

Supplement: Another good example is the Bundesjugendvertretung (Federal Youth Council, BVJ) in Austria which is the “legally anchored representation of the interests of all children and young people in Austria” (<https://bjv.at/english-information/>).

Theme 4

Mental health policy plans mentioned during the forum:

- In Slovenia, North Macedonia, but not specific for children. See for Slovenia e.g. : <https://www.nijz.si/sl/publikacije/mira-za-dusevno-zdravje-nacionalni-program-dusevnega-zdravja>
- Croatia: national plan for children, however not addressing the settings, physical environment. Addressing health and education. Mental health literacy and healthy living programmes with focus and financial resources for green areas.
- Dutch programme 'Kansrijke start'. <https://www.kansrijkestart.nl/>
- Developmental programme and support for teachers etc. needed (in Austria)
- Scandinavia first thousand day project reports: <https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1571297/FULLTEXT01.pdf> ; <https://www.norden.org/en/publication/first-1000-days-nordic-countries-situation-analysis> ; <https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1640984&dswid=-296>

Annex 2 Co-design workshop Skopje

Theme 3 Working towards translation of scientific results

Additional answers by the stakeholders.

We asked what the problems are on the interaction between stakeholders and scientists. What barriers do you see?

Some main answers:

- Difference in language within scientific community and in communication with decision-makers.
- Policy makers are sometimes impatient, while scientist too little sense of urgency.
- Policy makers have a certain goal and look for information supporting that. Coherency within stakeholder groups is lacking might add to this.
- Different sense of urgency. Motivation of scientist can differ from those of politicians.
- Politicians don't like precautionary principles.
- Poor listening, hearing, during all phases. Information during projects and not at the end.
- Additional barriers in communication: changing of politicians; different goals; education level differences; science is sometimes not applicable; too expensive.
- Timing is relevant and might differ between scientists and policy makers.
- Contacts are not always one-to-one, and thus 'interference' from other contacts might occur.
- The message itself can create a barrier as well. The meaning of the data can be unclear.
- Continuous exposure-response information needs to be provided versus yes/no/no information.
- Creative solutions: PR communicators or journalists, use media.
- We need media to transfer key messages from research and put more pressure on policy makers.
- Decision makers need different kind of information (yes or no) than scientists (can) provide. Thresholds are set based upon various arguments (incl. societal) and thus are always broader than the empirical results.
- Results do not always please policy makers. Policy makers are not (always) involved in research studies.
- Collaboration needs to aim to somehow practical wisdom and not to science or solutions.
- Scientific proposals could be used as examples of support to others to apply for research projects. So, less competition but more collaboration.
- There is an additional barrier between scientists and politicians because scientific papers are published in scientific journals which are not visible for politicians/policy makers.
- There is a need for systematic capacity building of scientists on their role in policy making process and learn how to communicate their findings to politicians.
- Research has to be proactive to bring main findings in front of messages.

Theme 4 Interventions 'bridging the gap' as a tool to improve health for all

Then, most of the session was about considering the following three phases.

Phase 1: Visual representation of steps in an intervention process (e.g. a logic model)

Phase 2: Where are considerations of social inequalities and an equity perspective relevant?

Phase 3: Questions relating to social inequalities and an equity perspective.

The results of the discussion in these phases are summarised below.

Phase 1: Building a general logic model

In relation to context/monitoring:

- working with municipalities, citizens, professionals/experts/researchers, national governments, EU/international governments, engineers and NGO's
- include experts like teachers -> ask them about problems and solutions + bring the topic to their agenda
- considering existing norms related to the topic
- use KPI's ('key performance indicators') to evaluate specific problems
- mention national-level problems
- deciding on a topic (-> evidence – what's changeable, what's integral?)
- consider innovators & Influences on different generations
- raise awareness on the intervention topic -> communication

In relation to implementation:

- raise awareness on the intervention topic -> communication

In relation to planning:

- Identify needs/problem in the very first step
- define the problem
- decide on the target (group)
- identification of affected groups
- Include experts like teachers -> ask them about problems and solutions + bring the topic to their agenda
- Considering existing norms related to the topic
- set up individual goals
- interventions for parents to educate them on the topic
- decide on the physical spaces and its access
- decide on the persons who execute the intervention

In relation to evaluation:

- Identify affected groups to perform the evaluation with them

- Inter-evaluation between the different planning steps/phases
- planning as a spiral procedure (planning -> implementation -> evaluation -> re-planning -> re-implementation -> re-evaluation...)
- putting the defined problem in the centre of evaluation, implementation and planning
- Use so-called KPI's ('key performance indicators') to evaluate specific problems

Phase 2 and 3:

In relation to an equity lens:

The texts below were transcribed from handwritten notes from the participants.

- Equity perspectives on the planning process
- Equity perspectives on the target groups -> planning process: Do we cover with interventions people with lower socio-economic status?
- Are there certain groups that are disadvantaged?
- Who's affected by interventions? (positive or negative)
- Who benefits?
- Do target groups get disadvantages?
- Do people have the ability to participate?
- Education in different social groups?
- Ad hoc communication strategy? (when decides outcome, how to communicate as part of the intervention, how to communicate depends on social factors)
- Moderating factors: poorness -> cultural differences, languages)
- To look at inequity is important: during planning, during monitoring, during evaluation (parents intervention), assessment of target population, but really every step
- Setting goals in the availability of the intervention
- Deciding on how it's implemented, availability for everyone – physical/online
- Monitoring the availability of the intervention (region and timely)
- Outcome, share, helping

Theme 5 Spectrum of prevention

A summary of bullet points of the suggestions by the participants:

- School settings can have both positive and negative effects. E.g. high demands, dress code (uniforms), school system (primary to secondary to high school selection), social norms, self-management requirements / capabilities
- Family: education, single parent, poverty, mental status parents, addiction, violence, crowding, number of children (can be a positive effect), divorce, moving house, trauma.
- Preventive programs, such as Dutch program "Nu Niet Zwanger" (not pregnant now).
- Community, housing, services, neighbourhood (playgrounds, green), social networks.

- Steppingstones in each life phase. We need to have universal knowledge, such as how many green areas are needed for children's mental health, what factors are risky? Things to fix and no-go's.
- Social tipping points:
 - 25% of the people make a tipping point occur.
 - Examples are given for different societal groups: Anti-vaxers; Fridays for future; White flight.
 - Education of parents on how to improve relationship with children and adolescents.
 - Force will not work. Surroundings are important. Small plans, too big does not work.
 - Collaborating social psychologists, psychologists, behaviour analysts – better understanding of human behaviour
 - Culture, religion, weather change, disasters, accidents, new people coming to the neighbourhood, crises
 - Social norms are detrimental, instances of sudden change, significant implications for welfare
 - Development of communication strategy to promote positive behaviour among children and parents. Children – teachers

Trend watching

For this session we used the method of asking repetitive 'why questions'. The starting question was: We do not meet our goal to protect children from mental health problems. Why?

What do you see coming?

Children's mental health is getting worse. Increase of depression, of anxiety. But is there a real increase or an increase of awareness, analysing, data collection? Allowing the conversation to happen will have higher numbers (and not so much increase the outcomes). Medicalisation could be a reason. The global, overall picture versus (differences in) regional pictures.

Theme 6

Annex 3 Stakeholder forum in Milano

Theme 4.2 World café sessions

Presenter: **MK**, University of Kaiserslautern, Cognitive and Developmental Psychology (online)

Title presentation: Effects of environmental exposures on mental health, well-being, and cognition in children at the transition from kindergarten to primary school: Concept of a longitudinal field study

World café questions:

- We study the relationship between greenspace, noise, air pollution, social factors, and the cognitive development of children in the period between preschool and primary school.
- From an intervention perspective what associations to analyse would be of most interest for you

World café discussion:

The presentation was regarded as very good, partly a bit hard to understand (particularly the different outcome measurements and how they are related to each other). But the study presented was regarded as quite illustrative about what Equal-Life is dealing with and is better to understand than the cohort data.

Topics/discussion points mentioned were:

- Identify quality aspects of green space that are important to children's development and how they relate to the preferences of their parents.
- Green spaces in residential areas are most important for small children.
- Study the relation between green spaces & quality of time spent in those spaces.

At that point, the group discussed what defines the beneficial quality of green spaces (or other places) in relation to the mental health of children. It was mentioned that the WP5 definition of "time spent" and "frequency spent" is probably a good indicator for an environment beneficial/attractive for children - better than defining "high quality" in terms of the physical features (vegetation, water ...). "Green space needs maintenance" was mentioned here.

The moderators mentioned that the Preschool study is also interested in social exposure/factors. The group discussion, therefore, shifted towards the role of green space for different (socio-economic) target groups.

Topics mentioned here by group 1 and the following groups were:

- Is there a difference in the effect of green space between different SES groups?
- Idea for an intervention: add green space to schools. Schoolyard itself is an equalizer of SES differences
- This provides equity of access to green space for pupils

More general ideas for intervention followed:

- Intervention should provide equity in architecture & urban design
- Bring nature inside the (artificial) city toward creativity
- Also, animals bring nature back to the city, not the standard elements more creative

- Consider the didactic aspects of green environment
- Designing an intervention that is located in a green space (free school lunch in a park during summer – Helsinki) => provides health-beneficial effects of green space and equity to different socio-economic groups

Besides green space, some groups' members suggested considering other exposures in the preschool study, namely:

- Include digital exposome
- Impact of electromagnetic radiation on preschool children
- Also include noise

Presenter: **CG**, Centre for Cognitive Science TU Kaiserslautern Germany (online)

Title presentation: Causal path modelling in Equal-Life. What has been and what will be done?

World café question:

How should (complex) empirical and statistical results be communicated to the target audience, and how to present these results, to avoid misconceptions?

World café discussion:

Stakeholders discussed that the answer depends on who the target audience is and that there are different levels of information that can be discussed. The stakeholders expressed interest in information on what the results represent and how to link it to interventions and practice. It is important to inform on the context of the results – what questions were asked, what data and methods were used, what data was missing, and how was the conclusion reached. It is also important for the stakeholders to know how they can change the outcomes in the real world. Regarding the form of presenting results, several forms were mentioned: short (written) summaries, interactive sessions with stakeholders, cartoons or animations, and interactive online materials. The results must be introduced properly, communicated in a user-friendly and simple way, and the relevance to the target audience should be clear.

Presenter: **AP**, TU Delft, the Netherlands

Title presentation: New methodological approaches to measuring the physical environment.

World café questions:

What metrics/indicators are you using in your daily practice (if at all) to assess a neighbourhood's walkability/accessibility/encouragement of active travel behaviour, etc.? What is lacking?

Do you use any available tools/design guidelines from global organizations such as WHO, UN Habitat, etc.? Which ones? What is lacking?

When it comes to improving children's mental health and well-being, which environmental aspects do you consider the most important and why? On what evidence do you prioritize them?

Do you see any potential in the work we presented for your daily practice? What would you need to make this happen?

World café discussion:

All participants agreed that the presentation was very good. Already knowing about this kind of research is an “eye-opener”. Members of this group discussion were impressed with all data gathered and were interested in how they can reach data at a similar level for their cases. They would be interested in reading reports and publications to read more about it on the Equal-Life website. Regarding the topic “green areas” they suggested to add also locations of schools/kindergartens, and playgrounds. Apart from the fact that green areas are discussed it is also important what such areas offer, what are activities supported in such places (recreation, use of digital apps ...). It was suggested that a list of aspects that spatial planners should consider before deciding on new interventions. Planners need active engagement of several stakeholders including residents and feedback from users. It is important to monitor and evaluate the use of the green area and make improvements with time. It is important to know what kind of green areas we need in the city (safety, activities ...). Accessibility is important, need to avoid barriers or cross them (railways ...). It should be a dynamic process. Tools for municipalities are needed to consider the list of aspects that they should consider.

Presenter: **JA & LG**, University of Bremen, Germany

Title presentation: Social Exposome - Concept, application fields, and implications

World café questions:

- Does our research inspire any practical implications in your work?
- Do you see any options to integrate our research in your work?
- Do you see any gaps, which should be addressed in our research?

World café discussion:

Do you see any gaps, which should be addressed in our research?

- One important aspect within Social Exposome should be digitalization and social media: Social reality is highly digitalized, and the increasing global digitalization should be considered when we refer to the social environment, because of the high interrelatedness between the real and the virtual/digital worlds.
 - Social reality is typically perceived through ‘digital filters’ (i.e. use of smartphones, iPads, social media, etc.)
 - The omnipresence of digital devices distracts from the real world and influences our relationships: distraction, loss of focus (e.g. parents and little children → parental investment)
 - Interaction effects between the use of digital advice and socioeconomic/educational background → digital literacy is needed
- When talking about the Social Exposome we also need to consider community and social interactions at the neighbourhood/district level.
 - Quality of neighbourhoods differs a lot within cities and depends highly on movement or employment patterns.
 - What can be observed is that segregation is wanted by the privileged residents/communities:
Important → How to break through this aversion and increase tolerance/ openness to achieve regeneration without losing benefits?

- Young families typically are a constant in neighbourhoods → maybe increase exchange platforms for children to reach acceptance between diverse populations → insight & exchange of living patterns
- Look for options to increase community involvement (participatory approach)
- When talking about social interactions we need to define the meaning of social interactions: quality and quantity of interactions
 - In practice it seems that interactions outside specific settings (e.g. school) define the atmosphere for meaning, because here interactions lose their function as “social roles” (e.g. teacher, pupil) but can grow into ‘true’ relationships. Thus, to ‘improve’ interactions, we need to create exchange options outside settings. This understanding may also help to improve neighbourhoods/relations within neighbourhoods
- For mental health social interactions are of high relevance, as we need to consider both, perception of interactions and behaviour within interactions
 - To improve communities/neighbourhoods we need money and, thus, we need to convince policy and decision-makers, we need to be outcome-related. But awareness is also highly important also can be outcome related.

Do you see any options to integrate our research into your work?

- Quality of data: Concrete operationalization options need to be defined to collect good & clean data to draw valid conclusions
- Reduction of complexity to make it feasible in the field – concrete guidelines would help
 - E.g. Logic Model for Equity Assessment: name concrete evaluation criteria that are to be followed in the development of interventions

Presenter: **MD**, TU Eindhoven, the Netherlands

Title presentation: Defining relevant settings by time-activity-sound exposure mapping

World café questions:

- Could you see this type of study being done in your municipality or another scale you are dealing with in your daily work (neighbourhood/city/province/country)?
- Do you see any benefit to apply our research in your daily work?
- Knowing the types of data we collected, what research questions come to mind? (In other words, can you give any additions/suggestions to our work?)

World café discussions:

Stakeholders found the idea of using behavioural patterns for data collection an interesting approach. The opinions were divided on whether or not they see this study being repeated in their own field of work, due to costs or privacy. The information that the stakeholders thought of to be beneficial for their work were: SES – noise, quality of life – noise, mental health – noise, and the social differences. It was suggested by the stakeholders to explore the relationship between duration and noise, with the question being: are locations with a higher noise exposure visited for a shorter time? Other suggestions were to connect more data to the existing dataset to investigate the mediation of other exposures such as green space and air quality and to incorporate subjective sound experience in the future. Finally, the stakeholders would like to see suggestions for interventions, guidelines for when a setting is “good” or “bad” and how to inform parents and teachers better about the effects of noise.

Presenter: **DK**, Jožef Stefan Institute, Department of Environmental Sciences, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Title presentation: Children's (mental) health and participatory research: diversity of levels of inclusion

World café questions:

- How to translate findings resulting from various participatory/CS activities in interventions?
- Which tools (and their features) are to be used for effective engagement of children - also to foster motivation and consequently sustainability of activities?
- Is there room for integration of approached presented into school curriculum?
- How to assess impact of activities/intervention considering specifics of participants (children) involved?
- How to foster the up scaling of the results and their uptake by policy and decision makers?

World café discussion:

In the beginning of the discussion, someone asked for an explanation on what is intervention. It seems that the meaning of the word is not sufficiently clear. Discussion went in direction that results from the research are very often not implemented in policies. Decision makers listen at the results coming from research, but they do not consider these results in decision making. We agree that environmental sensors for air pollution and noise exposure can give very valuable data and they should be shared with local authorities. People are sceptical of implementing solutions on children's science.

On the topic- Which tools (and their features) are to be used for effective engagement of children - also to foster motivation and consequently sustainability of activities, the participants gave very interesting proposals. These tools could be games, tools as amusement for children, tools that make children responsible to use, but still, they are not obligatory for children. It is also important to involve teachers and children, teachers could make rating for their development especially in development of emotional skills. Some of these tools could be included in education process and become part of education curriculum, especially for environmental pollution and human health.

We should think to include children in the process of development of tools—co-creation and co-design with children.

Someone gave idea for development of application for daily diary, so we can get picture for time activity patterns.

- How to foster the up scaling of the results and their uptake by policy and decision makers?

For this question all participants were very sceptical that results will be implemented in the policies.

Presenter: **KB**, senior advisor child & adolescent public health, the Netherlands

Title presentation: Mental Health in the Dutch Public Health sector

World café questions:

- Are you missing items in the wish list?
 - Well-being as a basic condition at school
 - More target group-oriented interventions
 - More accessible interventions; more preventive interventions
 - Attention to social and physical factors in relation to mental health
 - Data about: - young adults; - migrants; - low socio-economic status
 - More qualitative data in the field of mental health.
- Are there already qualitative data about mental health that you would suggest?

- Which qualitative data are most relevant?
- Are there already national research agenda's Mental Health on children's mental health?
- Can Equal-Life be of any support?

World café discussion:

Considering the time, no discussion was held on Karin's presentation.

Presenter: **ES**, City of Helsinki, Finland

Title presentation: Implementing evidence-based psychosocial interventions: an example from Helsinki, Finland

World café questions:

- What kind of national guidance is offered in your field of work?
- How would you apply your experiences in our work?

World café discussion:

First, time was taken to answer questions about the IPC-A intervention. For example, questions about the Finnish health care system in which basic health care to children is provided through the school system, and that the IPC-A is an individual intervention that can be provided by anyone who has completed the training. An important question for Emma is how to get managers in the school and healthcare system to adopt the IPC-A intervention. The intervention is already in the national guidelines; however, this national guidance is not enforced. Barriers in Finland are that managers do not feel that implementing healthcare interventions is part of their job description, as the law is more focused on prevention than interventions.

A few experiences from other countries with this issue were shared: one participant proposed to inform parents about the importance of this intervention so that they will ask schools to implement it. A German participant proposed to start screening for mental health problems to show the magnitude of the problem and create more support for implementing IPC-A or other interventions. Another German participant suggested that it might help to convince insurers that the intervention is cost-efficient, they might then lobby for the intervention in schools and healthcare settings. A participant from Italy proposed that it might help to inform university students about the importance of this intervention and the importance to work interdisciplinary, so that they might change the educational and healthcare systems of the future and will see the value of these interventions when they enter professional life. In Slovenia they encounter similar difficulties in implementing interventions, their barriers are mainly a lack of resources, people, and motivation, and who has the responsibility for the implementation of interventions is not clear.

Presenter: **MW**, NCJ, the Netherlands

Title presentation: Your brain in control?! Universal prevention towards mental health in adolescents

World café questions:

Is there a way in which Equal-Life can help measuring the changes we aim for with this intervention at school?

- we expect to see more interaction between students, outside classes and lunchbreaks

- we expect to see more interaction between students and teachers, outside scheduled classes, without self-reported research

In the sequel of the first question: Where can Equal-life help to get insights of change of behaviour by looking from another angle to the situation? In most research on groups and student there are lots of ethical discussions. Maybe there's a non-ethical part in Equal-Life that can be helpful.

World café discussion:

The 'Your brain in control' program is looking for (new) ways to evaluate the effects of the intervention. As with other universal prevention programs providing evidence on a single, specific intervention is challenging. A method could be to use social media and – in this case – YouTube videos and posted comments to track, analyse and classify 'the sentiments' (suggestion of / support by QUANTIA). Another question from the program is whether this intervention helps in improving and enhancing the social environment of schools. Will schools be a 'better setting', as researched by Equal-Life, due to this intervention? Can Equal-Life provide indications or causal relations on social environments, school settings, and children's mental health that would support this?

Presenter: **LG**, Cork City, Ireland

Title presentation: Let's play Cork

World café questions:

- Barriers to a more playful city include: dedicated full time resourcing, annual multi-stakeholder budgeting and public liability/insurance costs. Benefits of applying any result from Equal-Life in your daily work: research findings that properly clarify the importance of early preventative interventions. Applied research projects that test these findings would be a great benefit.
- In my presentation I will focus on 2 Cork examples - Let's Play Cork (Playful Paradigm) and Let's Grow Together (Infant and Childhood Partnership). It's important to note: Buy in for a more playful city is always easy – but there is a need for more applied research and committed pilot projects to grow confidence in the ability to deliver larger/more permanent playful city projects.

World café discussion:

- The main challenges are maintenance of the playgrounds and long-term funding. Collaboration between different sectors and departments, and people with different expertise are necessary for further development. That is a good reason for each city to have a healthy city coordinator who will coordinate all of them. Someone mentioned that children need digital equipment for playing in the playgrounds, this could be a very innovative idea.
- Very important is to consider equity principles to avoid enlarging the gap among different population groups. Lorcan thinks they considered social inequalities when they planned playgrounds.
- A festival of integrated involvement of children, parents, and other adults is an interesting event and important for emotional connection. This event was organized in Estonia, they are not so frequently organized, but they can be a good example of interpersonal connection.
- Evaluation of this intervention in Cork city was not performed, but Lorcan thinks that people are mostly satisfied. There was a proposal for evaluation of the intervention with walking

interviews, like walking through the city and asking people what they think and what will they change or add something else.

- Someone mentioned as a good example “playful benches in New Zealand”; benches in the green areas, with different possibilities for playing and stimulation of children’s development.

Presenter: **IŠ**, Urban Planning Institute of the Republic of Slovenia

Title presentation: Green spaces for healthier children and youth: recommendations from “Going Out for Health” programme in Slovenia

World café questions:

- What “additional” argumentation to support green space planning and design in practice can you give?
- How can the quality of outdoor living environment affect and improve the mental (and physical) health of children and youth.
- What kind of indicators can be used to measure that?

World café discussion:

- Questions that came up in the discussion were what the definitions are of ‘nature’ and ‘green space’, and that definitions probably differ in different settings. We should involve citizens in defining green spaces and what qualities they appreciate in them.
- Stakeholders also want more insights into how people react to different types of green spaces: what do people like and how is it beneficial to them?
- It is important to have green spaces close to homes and schools and on the routes children take to school, there is not enough data on this yet.
- Introduce digital tools for play in green spaces.

Presenter: **UB**, Social Protection Institute of the Republic of Slovenia

Title presentation: Is it all about location? Spatial Inequalities in the city of Ljubljana

World café questions

- What is the policy relevance and applicability of highlighted data?
- Are policy makers and political decision-makers interested in the results?

World café discussion:

- One question was if there are more inequalities between the areas, e.g.: Are there more facilities in general in the affluent areas? Is this quantifiable for future analysis?
- It was suggested to link the noise exposure data (e.g., from publicly available noise maps) to the data on kindergarten subsidies and see if there are differences in noise exposure depending on the prosperity status.
- We agreed that it is an innovative approach to estimate the prosperity of a neighbourhood and it could be considered to use in Equal-Life as well.

Keynote presentation **SD** (online)

The first 1000 days in the Nordic Countries

The first months and years of children's lives are paramount for their future well-being. Brain development is at its peak and foundations are laid for neural pathways and brain regions that dictate future learning, language, emotion regulation, and behaviour. This lays the foundation for good mental health throughout the lifespan.

The first 1000 days in the Nordic Countries is a three-year Nordic co-operation project launched in 2019. It has been working on an extensive situation analysis of the Nordic countries, reviewing the evidence-base for interventions and assessment tools, and development of policy recommendations. This resulted in three extensive reports on these three pillars.

For more information see: www.first1000days.is/about-the-project

Section 7 What are the next steps?

Stakeholder reflections

Tops:

- The highest evaluated part of the forum program was the workshop 'Evaluating children's access to public outdoor play space': engaging, easy, accessible
- Stakeholders highly valued the possibilities for informal discussions, they would have liked even more moments for this
- The combination of giving and receiving was appreciated
- Stakeholders appreciated learning more about the Equal-Life project
- The location and catering were highly valued

Tips:

- Stakeholders would have liked more breaks as the program was quite demanding and they liked informal interactions
- The number of presentations on different topics was too high for one moment for discussion afterwards (world café discussions)
- The technical equipment should have been tested before starting the sessions, or technical support needs to be available
- Define the level of interventions (from international to neighbourhood level).
- Stakeholders felt they did not know well enough what was expected from them before and during the forum, especially as stakeholders come from different fields and organizations

Suggestions for future stakeholder activities:

- It would be nice to be in a park when discussing parks and green spaces; add outdoor activities or site visits to the program
- Having one overarching topic to focus on might make it easier to concentrate, rather than having many different topics from different disciplines
- Use the stakeholders to test the project findings
- Organize additional activities between the in-person meetings to maintain and increase the cohesion of the network that was created in the forum, via digital means (e.g., Zoom or Teams)

Next steps discussed by Equal-Life researchers

With regards to future stakeholder communication and activities, the Equal-Life researchers discussed:

- Frequent (digital) information and updates
- Organizing continuing interactive (in-person) sessions for stakeholders and researchers
- To explore pilots or test projects of Equal-Life findings at stakeholder organisations
- To send save the date(s) for the next stakeholder activities
- In the first quarter of 2023, an agenda for stakeholder activities will be distributed

Annex 4 Co-design workshop in Como

Session on tools

We discussed the definition of tools and collected feedback on the type of tools considered.

During the session we returned to the concept of the tool. The list of project outcomes was shown, and we were asked to reason about the target concept.

Link to the presentation used to support the session:

<https://view.genial.ly/649cb440c29def001e132beb>

Notes from whiteboard/sticky notes on what can be linked to concept of tools: best practices, action perspective, interventions, training/education, application, software, questionnaire, skill, instrument, advice, device, series of webinars, guide, policy brief, 'the self', collection of data, collection of guidelines, e-learning, infographics. Interaction, intervention, practices, (self)assessment, policy making, measuring exposure data, build something, 'the other'.

Session on research questions

On table 1.

G: as a professional you see a child as a whole and therefore it is hard to distinct and prioritize singular factors. Awareness of optimal brain development is there; how exposures contribute or form a risk would be relevant knowledge.

M: focussing on (his task to) increasing children's mental health made prioritising easier (language, motor skills and well-being (nrs 2, 4 and 5). And be aware of the differences in Europe, different school systems, institutionalised inequalities.

On table 2.

G: sub questions under nr. 12. What is impact of chaotic environments and of supportive social environments, and what can we do to make a change?

E: sub questions under nr. 16 on internalizing behaviours. Related to the increase of eating disorders.

M: similar to Grace. Note: once you look for a problem, you will find a problem (example of mental health of Dutch girls).

For the toolbox: provide instructions on how to use the data, on what is known and on what is not yet known.

Access to services, use of and quality of is (maybe) lacking in the data. Part of cohort data and/or enriched data? If so, probably part of the social exposure.

On table 3.

Agreement was reached on the importance of questions on: How does a child's perspective of exposures differ from an adult's perspective? (nr 24) and are there subgroups of children that follow different exposome paths over life? (Nr 21.).

Built environmental factors is a crucial question as well to inform spatial planners.

Session on social exposome

Discussion notes:

Generally, the questions in Equal-Life are considered to be complicated questions. They are space dependent, contextual, cultural. In some cities noise is an issue, whereas in other cities it is air pollution. The expressed needs of citizens might not be the (health) issue or have the biggest impact on health.

More affluent neighbourhoods in Cork, have better green, playgrounds and lower exposures. In contrary to less affluent neighbourhoods where neglected, unsafe areas even are closed.

Social and infrastructural access of space for teenagers, girls is an item of concern.

Interesting tools: WHO HEAT tool on combined exposures and the Place Standard Tool.

Further suggestion: create participation of children in decision making: youth councils, youth representatives. But quite different to involve, various experiences.

A complex / combined model is interesting, but a specific action – coming out of the model – is key.

The social and physical environments are the contexts within which stress (of children and parents) occurs. This raises the question where to start at an individual level? Where to start at group, municipal, regional etc levels?

Maslov's hierarchy of needs: if the basis is unstable and the physical environment is continuously interfering, it is hard to intervene and address the mental health problems.

What is the impact of addressing problems, making (vulnerable) people aware of their health problems? Or something else?

Related to reducing inequalities: addressing the whole population versus specific groups? Example from Utrecht tool on 'equal opportunities'.

Multi level governance: how to strengthen interaction between various levels of government. What gaps need to be addressed?

Putting these topics / patterns on the (policy) agenda. Equal-Life will not be able to provide tailor-made solutions (managing the expectations).

The conceptual framework will be refined using the analysis outcomes of the different work packages in the project and of the stakeholder's input.

Through social interactions individuals are impacted by social and physical exposures.

Requests:

- for access to definitions of all the terms used in the social framework and in general. This suggestion is made in order to have a common language and understanding, for stakeholders as well as Equal-Life consortium members.
- Can children be involved be as well in meetings?

Interaction session: Social-environmental dimensions circle (taped on the floor).

Ljubljana: including social aspects and health impact assessments in spatial planning.

Integrating Equal-Life results into health impact assessments regarding mental health and cognitive development outcomes.

Session on Data and harmonization presented by JS (KI)

A presentation was given on mapping of existing content in the cohorts and harmonization (protocol) and code book.

There are Analysis teams on: diagnosis team (mental health), internalizing / externalizing (mental health), cognition, well-being, and on biomarkers. Selection of life phase where outcomes are (most) relevant.

Analysis plan:

- Which residential (maternal) physical and social exposures during pregnancy are associated with ADHD diagnosis?
- Which residential physical and social exposures at age 0-3 years are associated with an ADHD diagnosis?
- What is the association between prenatal physical and social exposome and an ADHD diagnosis? To what extent is this association mediated by preterm birth / SGA/LBW?
- What is the association between physical and social exposome at age 0-3 years and an ADHD diagnosis? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep (measured at age 0-3 year)?
- Which residential (maternal) physical and social exposures during pregnancy are associated with autism diagnosis?
- Which residential physical and social exposures at age 0-3 years old are associated with an autism diagnosis?
- What is the association between prenatal physical and social exposome and an autism diagnosis?
- What is the association between physical and social exposome at age 0-3 years and an autism diagnosis? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/ sleep (measured at age 0-3 years)?

Stakeholders' role was particularly relevant and valuable in interpreting the analysis outcomes. Move away from statistics into interpretation (RIVM- Irene van Kamp).

Related to data handling and future implementation of results.

Annex 5 Stakeholder forum in Helsinki

Summaries of presentations and discussions on the first day

Presentation: Overview of preliminary results /updates (DS, Zeus)

Aim of WP1 (on mechanisms) is to formulate theories and mechanisms, for how exposome links to mental health and cognitive development of children and adolescents and to understand how stress / restoration, self-regulation / coping and sleep may affect these relationships.

Research questions are studied in-depth in sleep and pre-school studies and in the cohort studies (data), enriched with new data. Examples of data available in the cohorts and/or are illustrated.

Reflections from stakeholders: coping, digital environment and daylight are (yet) missing in research. Outcomes influence the exposome; that arrow / link is 'missing' in the conceptual framework. This can be modelled though (in WP7).

This session provides feedback from the stakeholders to bring focus in the ongoing analysis of the results.

Presentation: Measuring access to public spaces (TUD)

This workshop consisted of two parts.

Part 1: In the first part, we examine which factors influence pedestrian access to public spaces and for whom. Using an interactive card game, we will prioritize different factors that affect pedestrian accessibility and discuss how we can practically measure them.

Part 2: In this second part we focus on how to assess children's access to greenspace in the city as a place to play, socialize, be active, and so on, ultimately contributing to healthy urban environments. Using interactive tools, we will collaborate to create ideal metrics for children's access to greenspace and discuss several metrics that have been implemented by TUD so far.

Related to part 1: SDGs, target 7: by 2030 provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities. How to identify, assess, establish / maintain these areas? Group work on what factors and for whom? And on measuring greenspace.

Identifying and prioritizing urban factors: overlap in factors, importance of proximity, shadow, safety, light and amenities. Most important factors are traffic, safety, followed by environmental factors, green, shade. Attractiveness and accessibility are key. Other factors mentioned are season of the year, availability of time, education / practice / norms.

Most important factors often are hard to measure, whereas those less important are easier to measure. For example: what is 'safety', how to measure this?

Reprioritizing specifically for particular population groups:

- for elderly new factors were identified such as free public transport, ice-free routes
- for children as well new factors were identified such as peers, distance from home, sidewalks / bike lanes

- for women not many changes occurred
- for persons with disabilities: accessibility is most important for this group, as well as safe transport.

Related to part 2:

Measuring green space for primary school aged children. What information would you need? For example, geographical size and detail, at neighbourhood level and/or national level?

Suggestions: adding wearables in order to collect data from children's movements, adding children's voice and perception on good environments. Another presentation was on cycling to work, adding data on private and public land, affordability, subsidized travel information, bicycle storage and seasonal maps. And another idea: "Let's play and move more outside", as children are not getting outside anymore. A variety of public places and increased attractiveness, voice of parents and of children. And plan and measure with the children.

TU Delft proposals:

- children's independent access to greenspace. It is good for children to go outdoors independently; can they reach a (green) space to play without crossing barriers?
- day to day greenspaces. Children go to school every day, but which streets do they pass and how vegetated are those?
- crowd-sourced perceived green spaces. Are data on greenspaces, such as OpenStreetMap and satellite images, complete? Or do they miss greenspaces?

Improvement suggestions: (social) safety of play areas, attractiveness of streets, add children's voice, use of black space and why these are not used (yet).

This session was related on how to use case scenarios related to access to public spaces. The feedback of the stakeholders is enabling TUD to further improve the modelling.

Presentation on enriching the environmental exposome: road traffic flow prediction and noise modelling (ULEIC)

Road traffic noise re-modelling and including in cohort studies (where needed). European standard modelling method (CNOSSOS-EU) is used to calculate noise exposures at facades of dwellings (and indirectly of individuals) from main roads. In epidemiological studies we need exposure data for smaller/ minor roads, for individual dwellings, and thus this approach according to the Environmental Noise Directive (END) is not ideal. Equal-Life is trying to fill in these gaps by using statistical methods with a selected number of variables (the so-called generalized linear mixed effects regression model). Such as road type, average daily traffic count, population, number of terminal / dead-end roads, nearest major road junction, gradient of the road, connectivity to other road types, number of people that can drive within 5 minutes to a particular location / drivetime. Road traffic flow predictions have been tested in UK, Barcelona; now used for 3D noise modelling.

Questions: What is the influence of electric vehicles? What about low noise emission zones? Dominant source and background noise differ per road type, thus at a residential road you will hear rolling noise whereas at a major road that will be engine noise.

No data on trees (canopies) is included in the modelling. Most challenging is the temporal aspect (and thus data) of road traffic.

This session provide knowledge and was an example of exposome mapping.

Social exposome (NIJZ)

Starting point before the presentation was the description of two main tools for the toolbox/guidebook planned from WP 4:

1) For the target group of researchers: Conceptual Framework of the Social Exposome and its implications for research. A short introduction will be given, the conceptual framework is already published (Gudi-Mindermann et al. (2023). Integrating the social environment with an equity perspective into the exposome paradigm: A new conceptual framework of the Social Exposome. Environmental Research. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.116485>).

2) For the target group of policy makers/urban planners/other stakeholders: Logic Model for Equity Impact Assessment and its implications for intervention planning and evaluation. After a short introduction a Case Study on Noise Legislation in Slovenia was presented.

Explanation of the social exposome conceptual framework, the integration of physical and social exposomes and the health outcomes and health inequalities. This is be tested in cohort studies and results expected in / after summer 2024. For the target group of policy makers, urban planners, public health authorities and others is the logic model a way to make an equity impact assessment. This is a tool to help embed an equity perspective in the planning, implementation and evaluation process of universal interventions to improve the built environment. Publication foreseen.

Suggestion: include a '#when?' question as well, in addition to How, Who, What and Where.

Case studies conducted in Equal-Life were (i) reduction of environmental noise exposures in Slovenia, (ii) improvement of bicycle infrastructure and increase of cycling behaviour in Macedonia, (iii) mobility hubs and (iv) play areas in Utrecht, the Netherlands. The environmental noise case study is further explained, see the handout / IC BEN conference paper as well.

In this session the stakeholders gave feedback on case studies and a model on the social exposome. This session is part of the workplan for implementation in practice.

Discussion on conceptual framework (INCHES)

The aim of this discussion was to get a picture of: (i) what 'type' of information can the different stakeholders apply in their work?, (ii) which data or results (exposures, mediators) are relevant to the work of stakeholders?, (iii) do stakeholders recognize their own dilemmas and questions that they have in the first results and deviate this from what stakeholders expected, in their work? (e.g. what are the main causes and perhaps mediators for mental health in children, according to the Equal-Life researchers and according to the stakeholders?).

An interactive game was played to get an idea which kind of exposures were prioritized by the stakeholders: physical exposures, mediators or social exposures. In addition, sticky notes were produced. Some outcomes were:

Social exposures were highly rated as being important.

Children's voices need to be and can be heard.

Where is most impact to be expected? In the decision-making systems. There change can be best achieved.

This session is part of the workplan for implementation in practice.

Summaries of presentations and discussions on the second day

Case study: City collaboration track, Improving young people's sense of safety in the city (MV)

Bloomberg and Harvard City Leadership Initiative support, in Helsinki. Public value statement: enabling a safe and welcoming environment for children throughout the day is good for each individual and the community. Tackling the issue by breaking it down into sub causes and identifying complexities by an interdisciplinary team. E.g. lack of safe free time activities for the young, behavioural issues among the young at school and in the streets. Growing number of confrontations between groups, lack of support and sense of belonging for families.

Three entry points have been selected:

- Services are designed for 'average' users
 - o Hobby platform
 - o Co-create services with children
 - o New area-based leadership model
 - o Etc.
- Lack of safe free time activities for young
 - o Families have knowledge about free time possibilities for children
 - o Proactive leisure services find young people without hobbies
 - o Etc.
- Public spaces (incl schools) are experienced as unsafe
 - o Intervening and solving every case of bullying and harassment
 - o Public space improvements and new school building are prioritized
 - o Placemaking interventions with children
 - o Etc.

Lessons are integrated into regular work practices.

Problem Driven Interactive Adaptation (PDIA) process (Harvard) steps: Initial problem analysis; Identify action steps; Take action; Check-in; Sustain authority and legitimacy; Adapt and iterate.

Key results and take aways:

- We managed to complete numerous simultaneous joined interventions in the area in matter of months. Initial results indicate that anti social behaviour has decreased in the area.
- Start with the problem and the root causes. Stopping at the common problem was worth the time – this enhanced people's ownership and from an early stage they started seeing their role in the solutions too.

- Make sure you have the right people at the table. Having the mandate to bring about concrete change and interventions was crucial.
- Interventions were based on wide participation of stakeholders and a solid knowledge base.

Qualitative data collection (and use) needs to be improved. Qualitative data will be combined with the existing (quantitative) data in the municipality. Then a decision on form(at) of data collection will be taken.

What happens next?

- Results are compiled and presented to the city leadership. Decisions are yet to be made about scaling.
- All city divisions are committed to strengthening area-based work, utilizing the tools and process trialed in the area.
- Good work continues in the area and similar work will be expanded to the surrounding neighborhoods
- Key challenge to address: the core group of 8 people put a lot of time into this and received coaching throughout the process – how do we utilize the methods in existing cooperation structures?

Case study: infant mental health (TL- Healthy Cities Cork)

Cork city: Let's grow together! Various interconnected strategies: infant mental health and well-being; speech language communication and literacy.

Early environmental quality: presentation preliminary results (JS, Karolinska Inst.)

A combination of birth cohort data and data from school studies.

FAIR cohort: ADHD most important variables (during pregnancy) are birthyear, income, smoking, population density, road intersection closeness, education of father, road distance, etc. For Autism the most important variables are income, green urban areas, build-up area, road noise, green urban area, foreign citizenship, etc. Other results are available from the ALPINE, PIAMA and WALNUTS cohorts.

Question: how to communicate the results?

- Communicate the results per cohort or all pooled cohorts?
- Visualize the importance of the variables. Or a top ten presentation.
- Infographic
- More information is needed, for example on causality, how to interpret the relation between the variable and the outcome.
- Involve stakeholders in reviewing papers! In order to give meaning to research outcomes.

Presentation by LA on Personal listening and IT devices and their relation to lifestyle of adolescents in the Slovak Risk Behavioural Survey

The study is based on a bilateral US-Slovak project to evaluate the impact of selected behavioral, psychological, and socioeconomic factors on adolescent health in the Bratislava agglomeration. Special

attention is paid to the use of selected IT devices (TV, PC - personal computers, personal music players - PMPs). The data from 525 students (185 boys) attending 8 secondary schools in Bratislava, aged 15-20 years are presented. The most important health risk behaviors in the students' sample were identified, 90.9 % of students listen to PMP on average for 405 minutes and use mobile phones for 384 minutes per week, significantly more girls. About 50 % of students listen to PMPs more than 200 minutes a week. Those students have a worse lifestyle than those listening to PMPs less than 200 minutes a week. A high percentage of PC usage has been observed, especially during the weekend (72.1% more than three hours per day), and less interest in watching TV. Students use the PC more than their parents and watch less TV, but when watching it, they copy the behavior of both parents. The study presents a challenge for the analysis and for future prevention as well as intervention activities to protect and promote the health of children and youth.

Place Standard Tool for Children and Young People (JH, City of Glasgow)

The Place Standard tool (PSt) was launched in 2015 and in response to on-going feedback a [version for children and young people](#) was co-produced and published in 2022. This tool provides a practical solution to help younger communities identify in a collaborative and inclusive manner what works well within their place, what needs improving and the solutions to address these. The tool is made up of 14 place dimensions which align with the UN SDGs and this relationship coupled with the successful application of the tool across Europe has led to an invitation from WHO to Public Health Scotland (PHS) to host a new Collaborating Centre for Place from 2024 onwards. The lessons learned from the Equal Life Project would be invaluable contribution to the Collaborating Centre's programme.

The sessions above are related to knowledge sharing. It gives the Equal-Life consortium insight in which kind of policy implementations and potential interventions are important.

Annex 6 Some examples of used personas

Co-design process

Co-design is a design-led process that uses creative and participatory methods. There is no onsize-fits-all approach. Instead, there are patterns and principles that can be applied in different ways with different people. Importantly, co-designers make decisions, not just suggestions ([Burkett, 2012](#))

Source: <https://www.yacwa.org.au/wpcontent/uploads/2016/09/An-Introduction-to-Co-Design-by-Ingrid-Burkett.pdf>

Design thinking

- Context analysis
 - Stakeholder segmentation
 - Wishes
 - Aims
 - Position
 - Influence
 - Personas
 - Behaviour
 - Attitude
 - Missing partners

<https://g8mvf9i2x72.typeform.com/to/K6PpU2xZ?typeformsource=www.linkedin.com>

Design thinking

3 phases

- Empathize - understand and share the feelings of another
- Define - to determine or identify the essential qualities or meaning of whatever defines the problem
- Ideate - a creative process where designers generate ideas in sessions

DESIGN THINKING: A NON-LINEAR PROCESS

Principles of co-design

Annex 8 Working on application of tools

Different design and participation approaches, focusing on where power is held and in whose interests it is exercised.

These things are transactional at best, harmful, degrading and violent at worst		
Approach	Keywords	Where power is held
Designing at people	Designer, professional or policy-maker as expert, top-down decision-making	<i>Designing at people</i> is about what decision-makers and designers think and want.
Designing for people	Design thinking, anything 'centred' e.g. human-centred (HCD), user-centred (UCD), patient-centred, citizen-centred design etc.	<i>Designing for people</i> is about what designers and decision-makers want to know and achieve. Good intent usually ends up as system-centred, designer-centred, executive-centred or staff-centred by implementation.
These things are transformational at best, however they are not inherently inclusive or equitable		
Designing with people and planet	Co-design, participatory design, deliberative democracy	<i>Designing with people</i> is about what matters to people with lived experience and decision-makers (co-decided).
Led by the people	Co-production, community-led design, citizen movements, design justice*	<i>Led by the people</i> is about what people, families and communities want for themselves.

Kelly Ann McKercher, 2020

What is the 'social movement' part of co -design?

To make co -design a reality, we need systems, organisations and communities to embrace the leadership and contributions of people with lived experience. Doing that requires different ways of thinking and being, which are missing from many teams, organisations and systems. The table below describes several social movements that are necessary to make co -design a reality and a norm.

Social movement aspects of co-design

From	To
Making decisions for people with lived experience	Making decisions with people with lived experience
Valuing professional expertise above all	Valuing professional and lived experience equally
Seeing marginalised people as a burden	Seeing marginalised people as resilient, creative and capable
Colonising, heteronormative and ableist systems	Compassionate systems that see and respond to dimensions of difference
Believing that resources are scarce to make change	Seeing an abundance of experience, ideas and energy for change
Focusing on 'consumer' councils and committees	Embedding participation in everyday practice
Rushing to solutions	Slowing down to listen, connect and learn

McKercher, K. A. (2020). *Beyond Sticky Notes. Doing Co-design for real: mindsets, methods and movements.*

Process

Building the conditions

.... Through focusing on relationships, widening inclusion and offering genuine invitation that encourage people to share their strengths

Develop frameworks for safety

.....e.g. frameworks for serious disclosure, safe disclosure, frameworks for recognition, attribution and payment (compensate/pay your co-designers)

Annex 9 research questions used in Como co-design workshop

Research questions

Session 3. Topic: **Research questions**

The aim of this session is focus on the use of our research results to the world of policymaking.

Therefore, we would like to ask you to do some homework before the meeting in Como.

We have a range of research questions.

Table 1 shows an overview of external exposome questions in association with cognitive and mental health outcomes. These are overarching research questions.

Table 2 shows the outline for a list of questions focusing on a combination of selected exposures (external and internal). These questions are also anticipated as overarching research questions. In this list of questions, there are 7 core questions which are then repeated for the 9 different outcomes that are of interest in Equal-Life. These targeted questions aim to take into account both the cumulative effects and the life-course perspective in analysing the effects of different combinations of exposures on mental health and cognitive outcomes. The targeted analysis will also include mediators, modifiers and re-reversed causality (bi-directional) analyses.

In addition to the main research questions in Equal-Life, in Table 3, we have gathered questions that are specific to studying the associations between different types of exposomes (e.g., social exposome, physical exposome).

As homework we would like to ask you to choose for each table the three questions that you consider the most relevant.

You may have specific criteria that support your decision. Please take note of your arguments to select your preference questions.

You might consider arguments based on feasibility to make interventions, on the biggest health impact, on cost-benefit reasons, on supporting current projects, or any other reason. You also have arguments why some research questions are not good, not feasible or maybe not just or ethical.

Do you consider research questions as such are valuable for stakeholders like policy makers or only the results?

Can you bring your filled in forms to Como.

However, we prefer it if you could send us your filled in forms two days before so we can print them out.

In the session related to the Equal-Life questions we will discuss your feedback on the research questions.

Table 1. Research questions on the overarching external exposome

Question #	Research question	Exposure	Outcome	Time windows of exposure	Time windows of outcome
1	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with nonverbal IQ?	External exposome (physical + social)	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
2	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with the Language development?	External exposome (physical + social)	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
3	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with grades?	External exposome (physical + social)	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
4	Which exposures in residential and pre-school settings are associated with motor skills?	External exposome (physical + social)	Motor skills	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
5	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school setting are associated with Well-being?	External exposome (physical + social)	Well-being (including life satisfaction, quality of life. etc.)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence

6	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with Internalizing symptoms?	External exposome (physical + social)	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
7	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with Externalizing Symptoms?	External exposome (physical + social)	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
8	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with Thought disorders?	External exposome (physical + social)	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
9	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with the p-factor?	External exposome (physical + social)	p-factor (index-variables)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, 13-16	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
10	Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings during a child's life are associated with internal biomarkers of mental health and what time windows are most important?	External exposome (physical + social)	Internal biomarkers of mental health	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

Table 2. Research questions on selected list of exposures (social and/or physical) and outcomes of interest to Equal-Life.

Question #	Research question	Exposure	Outcome	Mediator	Time windows of exposure	Time windows of outcome
11	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with nonverbal IQ?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11a	How does the irregularity, unpredictability, and duration of social and physical risk factors affect Non-verbal IQ in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on non-verbal IQ later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

11c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on non-verbal IQ later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or Physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's non-verbal IQ outcomes?	Physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's non-verbal IQ outcomes?	Social exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
11f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's non-verbal IQ?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Non-verbal IQ (including attention, working memory, short- and long-term memory, and executive functions)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

12	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with language development?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect language development in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on language development later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on language development later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

12d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's language development?	Physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's language development?	Social exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
12f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's language development?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Language development (including Verbal-IQ, dyslexia, and verbal and reading comprehension)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
13	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with school achievement?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)

13a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect school achievement in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on school achievement later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on school achievement later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)

13d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's school achievement?	Physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's school achievement?	Social exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
13f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's school achievement?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	School achievement (including grades and, arithmetic and language tests)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	7-12, adolescence (might change between countries)
14	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with motor skills?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)

14a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect motor skills in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on motor skills later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on motor skills later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)

14d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's motor skills?	Physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's motor skills?	Social exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
14f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's motor skills?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Motor skills	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	0-2, 3-6, (7-12, adolescence)
15	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with well-being?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being))	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence

15a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect well-being in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on well-being later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on well-being later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	4-6, 7-12, adolescence

15d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's well-being?	Physical exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's well-being?	Social exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
15f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's well-being?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Well-being (including: quality of life, eudonic well-being and hedonic well-being)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	4-6, 7-12, adolescence
16	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with Internalizing behaviours?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

16a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect internalizing behaviours in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on internalizing behaviours later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on internalizing behaviours later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

16d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's internalizing behaviours?	Physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's internalizing behaviors?	Social exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
16f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's internalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Internalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). Anxiety, Depression, and Eating disorder (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Depression/anxiety: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
17	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence

17a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect externalizing behaviors in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on externalizing behaviors later in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on externalizing behaviors later in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence

17d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
17f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's externalizing behaviors?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Externalizing Symptoms (measured by psychometric tests). ADHD and Conduct disorders (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis ADHD: 6-12 Diagnosis Conduct D: 5-6, 7-12, adolescence
18	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with Thought disorders?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

18a	How does the <i>irregularity, unpredictability, and duration</i> of social and physical risk factors affect thought disorders in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on thought disorders later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on thought disorders later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

18d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's thought disorders?	Physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's thought disorders?	Social exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
18f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's thought disorders?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	Thought disorders (measured by psychometric tests). Autism (as diagnosis)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	SDQ: 3-6, 7-12, 13-16 Diagnosis Autism: 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
19	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with p-factor?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16

19a	How does the irregularity, unpredictability, and duration of social and physical risk factors affect p-factor values in children across their life-course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19b	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on p-factor later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19c	Is there a cumulative effect of the physical <i>out-door</i> environment and social exposome in early life stage on p-factor later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6	3-6, 7-12, 13-16

19d	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's p-factor outcomes?	Physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19e	Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's p-factor outcomes?	Social exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
19f	Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's p-factor outcomes?	Selected list of exposure indicators from physical exposome	p-factor (index-variables)	Sleep/ stress/ self-regulation	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	3-6, 7-12, 13-16
20	How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with biomarkers of mental health (identified by WP2)?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Biomarkers of mental health	-	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence

20a	How do internal biomarkers mediate the pathway from physical and social exposures in early life to mental health and cognitive outcomes?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome	Different outcomes identified in Equal-Life	Internal exposome (biomarkers of mental health)	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence	Pre-/perinatal, 0-2, 3-6, 7-12, adolescence
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Table 3. Research questions on associations between social and physical exposome

No	Research question	Exposures
21	Are there subgroups of children that follow different exposome paths over life?	Critical life events, socio-economic status, migrant background, area of residence (urban/rural), gender, etc.
22	What cumulative measures (scores) for external exposome can be made? a) what parts of exposome are stable over time b) what parts of exposome are highly correlated	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome
23	Are built environmental factors merely spatially correlated or do some mediate the effect of others?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome that relate to the built environment, such as population density, greenspace, noise, air pollution, street connectivity
24	How does a child's perspective of exposures differ from an adult's perspective?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome
25	How do individual and combined exposure patterns change over a child's life course?	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome
26	How do social exposures determine variation in physical exposures? (exposure differential)	Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome

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| 27 | How do physical exposures determine the variation in social exposures? | Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome |
| 28 | Development of new exposure assessment models and indicators and comparison of exposure metrics obtained from different sources | Selected list of exposure indicators from both social and/or physical exposome |

